

1 **Protic ionic liquid-based extraction of potentially**
2 **toxic elements from digested sewage sludges with**
3 **ecotoxicological and bioavailability assessment of**
4 **residues**

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21 **ABSTRACT**

22 Agricultural use of sewage sludges (SSLs) aligns with the principles of sustainable development and
23 circular economy. Nonetheless, SSLs frequently contain higher contents of potentially toxic elements
24 (PTEs), which may limit their environmental use. The aim of this study was to use protic ionic liquids
25 (PILs), characterized by different properties (1-methylimidazolium chloride ([H₁Cim]Cl),
26 triethylammonium hydrogen sulfate ([TEA][HSO₄]), and 1-methylimidazolium hydrogen sulfate
27 ([H₁Cim][HSO₄])) to remove PTEs from digested SSLs. Apart from assessing removal efficiency, the
28 mechanisms of action of specific PILs were identified as well as the bioavailability of the PTEs and the
29 toxicity of the residue after the removal of the PTEs were determined. [H₁Cim]Cl was characterized by
30 the highest metal extraction efficiency. By using this solvent, from 11% to 89% of the PTEs was
31 removed, among which Zn, Cd, and Cu were removed most effectively. However, the efficiency of the
32 other PILs was relatively lower. The extraction efficiency was affected by temperature, SSL-to-PIL
33 ratio, ethanol washing, and SSL type. The treatment of the SSLs with [H₁Cim]Cl significantly reduced
34 the contents of some bioavailable PTEs. The leachates toxicity was influenced by SSL types and
35 organisms. However, the toxicity of the SSL leachates was observed to decrease (by 14-87%) after
36 treating the SSLs with [H₁Cim]Cl. The statistical analysis found that Ni and Zn could have been the
37 critical factors determining the SSLs' toxicity to bacteria, whereas As towards plants. The results
38 confirm the high efficacy of the proposed method, which can be a promising solution supporting circular
39 economy-based management of SSLs.

40

41 *Keywords:* Waste management; Environmental sustainability; Toxicity; Aqueous leachate; *Lepidium*
42 *sativum*; *Aliivibrio fischeri*

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46 **1. Introduction**

47 The population growth causes an increased food demand, which requires intensification of
48 agricultural production in terms of both yield quantity and quality. One of the methods to improve
49 agriculture efficiency is the use of fertilizers. Anthropogenic nutrient-rich organic waste is a good
50 alternative to synthetic fertilizers. Sewage sludges (SSLs) belong to this group [1]. Such an approach
51 perfectly fits the global sustainable development and circular economy strategies [2]. Given the growing
52 production of SSLs in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs), it is of key importance to properly manage
53 and reuse them, particularly in accordance with the safety rules. Although SSL has many advantages
54 from its desirable components (organic matter (OM), micro- and macronutrients), it contains undesirable
55 components such as pathogens, potentially toxic elements (PTEs), and different organic compounds [3].
56 Among them, PTEs are an important group, very frequently limiting the use of SSL as a bio-based
57 fertilizer.

58 In spite that some PTEs at trace amounts are necessary for plant physiological functions and growth,
59 they can yet exhibit a toxic effect when their concentrations exceed the critical levels [4]. In particular,
60 PTEs such as Cd, Pb, Ag, As, or Al are highly toxic and do not perform any known biological functions
61 in plants [5, 6]. According to the Council Directive 86/278/EEC [7, 8], SSLs require stabilization before
62 their use in agriculture. The stabilization processes, such as anaerobic digestion or composting, stabilize
63 OM [9] and eliminate pathogens [9, 10] and many organic contaminants [11], but the end products still
64 contain certain concentration of PTEs [12]. A long-term use of such materials containing PTEs may
65 result in their accumulation in the soil, in consequence leading to farmland soil contamination and
66 reduced productivity [13]. Moreover, PTEs can be leached into groundwater and surface water, thus
67 posing a direct threat to human health due to their accumulation in aquatic organisms and drinking water
68 [14]. The elimination of PTEs from digested SSL before its incorporation into the environment is
69 becoming a key issue and the development of efficient methods for removing these elements can
70 significantly boost the possibility of safe use of SSL in agriculture, minimizing the environmental and
71 health risks.

72 There are a number of methods for removing PTEs from SSLs [15], but they usually have a range
73 of drawbacks. For instance, the most eco-friendly biological processes based on microorganisms
74 oxidizing sulfide compounds of PTEs into ionic forms are time-consuming [16, 17] and lead to the
75 consumption of nutrients present in the SSL by the added microorganisms [18]. The chemical methods
76 based on inorganic acids (e.g. H_2SO_4) and organic acids (citric acid, oxalic acid), in turn, require a low
77 pH, which causes corrosion of the process equipment and the subsequent need to neutralize the product
78 [19]. Furthermore, inorganic acids are non-selective and this means that they can extract not only PTEs,
79 but also other substances, which may hinder resultant functionality of the obtained extract [20]. The
80 application of H_2SO_4 may also lead to the formation of sulfates, which can have an adverse
81 environmental impact [21].

82 Ionic liquids (ILs), which can overcome the limitations of conventional chemical extraction
83 methods, may serve as an alternative to the above-mentioned substances or processes. The class of protic
84 ionic liquids (PILs), being an important subgroup of ionic liquids (ILs), has lately attracted considerable
85 attention [22]. PILs are characterized by good solubility, chemical, electrochemical, and thermic
86 stability, biocompatibility, immiscibility in some organic solvents, and synthesis simplicity. In recent
87 years, research has been conducted on the use of PILs to remove PTEs from biomass, including wood
88 waste [23, 24] and willow harvested after soil phytoextraction [25]. However, only a few studies deal
89 with SSLs [26–28].

90 The earlier studies regarding SSL largely focused on the optimization of the PTE extraction process
91 [26–28], but there is a lack of comprehensive analyses explaining the mechanisms of this process. By
92 using various PILs with different structures, an attempt was made in this work to indicate the key cation
93 (aliphatic vs. aromatic) or anion structure (simple vs. complex) in order to identify the mechanisms
94 responsible for the effective extraction of PTEs. An additional novelty aspect of this study is a holistic,
95 physico-chemical and ecotoxicological assessment of PIL-treated SSLs (i.e., the residues after the PIL-
96 treatment). Existing research predominantly focused on PIL recovery, whereas the management of PIL-
97 treated SSLs remains a poorly recognized issue. The literature completely lacks information what
98 properties PIL-treated SSL has in both physico-chemical and ecotoxicological terms. The physico-

99 chemical and ecotoxicological characteristics of the residues are an essential issue before its further use.
100 As far as the potential use of PIL-treated SSLs as a soil amendment is concerned, it is of essential
101 significance to understand the impact of processed SSLs on living organisms. It is necessary to assess
102 the possible effects of SSLs, after their treatment with PILs, on the environment. This type of research
103 has not been conducted thus far, in spite of the existing reports that PILs can be toxic to different groups
104 of organisms [29].

105 The aim of the present study was to identify the mechanisms of extraction of PTEs from different
106 digested SSLs using PILs with diverse properties and to assess residue after the PIL-based extraction,
107 including physico-chemical and ecotoxicological analysis. This research is designed to develop an
108 effective and safe method for removing PTEs, which will allow SSLs to be reused in agriculture with
109 minimal environmental and health risks.

110

111 **2. Materials and methods**

112 **2.1. Characteristic of digested SSLs**

113 The SSLs were obtained from municipal (mechanical-biological) WWTPs located in southeastern
114 part of Poland: Chełm (SSL1, 51°07'56''N 23°28'40''E) and Zamość (SSL2, 50°43'14''N
115 23°15'30''E). Both WWTPs primarily handle urban wastewater with limited contributions from
116 industrial sources. However, the amount of industrial wastewater, expressed in terms of population
117 equivalent (PE), is higher at the Chełm WWTP (PE = 17 408, 17% of total) compared to the Zamość
118 WWTP (PE = 7 235, 9.0% of total). In Chełm, industrial wastewater is mainly produced by food
119 industry, including a dairy cooperative, a fruit concentrate producer, and a brewery. In Zamość, the
120 industrial sources include the food industry (grain mills, a feed mill, a cold store, a dairy cooperative),
121 the wood industry (a furniture factory), and the metal industry.

122 The SSLs were biologically stabilized using two different mesophilic temperatures, with SSL1 at
123 39°C and SSL2 at 34°C. After digestion, different dewatering techniques were applied – a decanter

124 centrifuge for SSL1, and a filter press for SSL2. For SSL1, an additional step of pre-drying the samples
125 was performed in an automated solar dryer (glasshouse type). Several representative subsamples were
126 collected after this stage. All subsamples were then mixed and air-dried for several weeks. Using a
127 laboratory knife grinder (Testchem, Poland), the samples were ground to particles no larger than 3 mm.
128 The final drying step took place in a laboratory dryer (Wamed, Poland) at $35 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ until the samples
129 reached a constant weight. The prepared SSL fractions were stored in glass containers in the dark until
130 PIL treatment. Detailed information about the characterization methods for both untreated and treated
131 SSLs can be found in the **Supporting Information (SI)**.

132

133 **2.2. Protic ionic liquids (PILs)**

134 Three PILs (with >98% purity) were used: 1-methylimidazolium chloride ($[\text{H}_1\text{Cim}]\text{Cl}$),
135 triethylammonium hydrogen sulfate ($[\text{TEA}][\text{HSO}_4]$), and 1-methylimidazolium hydrogen sulfate
136 ($[\text{H}_1\text{Cim}][\text{HSO}_4]$). PILs were chosen based on differences in cation type (aliphatic vs. aromatic), anion
137 type (derived from hydrogen acid vs. oxyacid) and melting points ranging from 64°C to 90.5°C . The
138 PILs were purchased from IOLITEC, Ionic Liquids Technologies GmbH (Heilbronn, Germany),
139 contained trace water measured by Karl Fischer titration. The PILs contained equivalent amounts of
140 cations and anions (99.9%).

141 To reduce viscosity, the PILs were diluted with 20% (w/w) ultrapure water (Labopol-Polwater,
142 Poland; $\text{EC} < 0.05 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), accounting for their existing water content. Previous research by Abouelela
143 et al. [26] showed this water level optimize PTEs extraction using $[\text{H}_1\text{Cim}]\text{Cl}$. **Table 1** presents the
144 detailed physico-chemical properties of both the pure PILs and their aqueous solutions.

145

146 **2.3. Removal of PTEs from digested SSLs**

147 A modified method based on Yao et al. [28] was used to optimize the removal PTEs from SSL.
148 First, 2 g of SSL was mixed with 10 g of PIL solution (solid/liquid ratio (S/L ratio) 0.2) and heated at

149 either 90°C or 115°C to find the optimal temperature for PTEs extraction. Next, at the optimal
150 temperature, a larger SSL amounts were processed with 10 g of PIL solution (S/L ratio 0.35 or 0.5) to
151 improve extraction efficiency and cost effectiveness. Finally, the number of ethanol washings (1-4 times,
152 plus Soxhlet extraction) was optimized to reduce ethanol use while effectively separating PIL and PTEs
153 from SSL. Specifically, SSL was added to 15 mL pressure tubes containing PIL solution, mixed
154 thoroughly, and heated for 45 minutes based on prior findings that longer times had little impact [28].
155 After cooling, the mixtures were transferred to 50 mL tubes using 40 mL of 99.9% ethanol. The tubes
156 were vortexed, left for 1 hour, vortexed again, and centrifuged at 3,000 rpm for 45 minutes. The solids
157 were decanted, fresh ethanol added, and washing repeated four times. The washed SSL was then placed
158 in a cellulose thimble for Soxhlet extraction at 135°C using 150 mL ethanol for 25–30 cycles. Finally,
159 the treated SSL was dried overnight in a fume hood and then at $35 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ until constant weight. Pseudo-
160 total PTE content in untreated and treated SSLs was measured by ICP-OES after acid digestion (HNO_3
161 + HCl, 3:1). More details are in the **SI**.

162

163 **2.4. PTEs bioavailability**

164 To determine the bioavailability of PTEs in PIL-treated and non-treated SSL, 1 g of SSL was mixed
165 with 10 g of ultrapure water (9.1%, w/w) in 50 mL centrifuge tubes. The mixtures were agitated on a
166 rotary stirrer at 10 rpm for 24 h. Following this, the tubes were centrifuged at 3,000 rpm for 10 min. The
167 resulting suspensions were filtered through quantitative paper filters with a pore diameter of 3-5 μm into
168 15 mL centrifuge tubes. The funnels were rinsed with a small amount of ultrapure water to ensure
169 complete transfer. To each sample, 1 mL of 65% HNO_3 was added, and the extracts were diluted with
170 ultrapure water to a final volume of 12 mL. The analysis was conducted in the same manner as for the
171 pseudo-total content of PTEs. The bioavailability index (BI) was calculated to quantify the concentration
172 of PTEs extracted with water (representing the bioavailable fraction) relative to their pseudo-total
173 content. The BI was calculated using the following equation (**Eq. 1**):

$$174 \quad BI = \left(\frac{C_{bio}}{C_{total}} \right) \cdot 10\,000 \quad (1)$$

175 where C_{bio} is the concentration of PTEs extracted with water, and C_{total} is pseudo-total content of PTEs.
176 The factor of 10 000 was applied solely to normalize the values and facilitate comparison.

177

178 **2.5. Toxicity assessment of digested SSLs**

179 SSL samples, both before and after treatment, were evaluated using two liquid phase tests:
180 Phytotestkit F Test and Microtox[®]. The liquid phase was prepared according to the EN 12457-2 protocol
181 [30]. The SSL samples were mixed with ultrapure water at a solid-to-liquid ratio of 100 g/L, then shaken
182 in glass bottles on a rotary stirrer at 10 rpm for 24 h. The leachates were filtered through 0.45 µm porosity
183 filters and the resulting solution was used for further analysis.

184 The Phytotestkit F Test evaluates the decrease or absence of seed germination and the growth of
185 young roots after exposing seeds of selected higher plants to chemical compounds in 20 mL of SSL
186 leachates, compared to a control using ultrapure water. The test plant used was cress (*Lepidium sativum*),
187 and the experiment was conducted in triplicate. After 3 days of incubation at 25°C, the analyses and
188 measurements of *L. sativum* length were performed using Image Tool 3.0 for Windows (UTHSCSA,
189 San Antonio, USA). To determine the half maximal effective concentration (EC_{50}) of the chemical
190 compounds in the SSL leachates, the phytotoxicity was assessed for leachates diluted (v/v) to 4.5%
191 (twofold), 2.3% (fourfold), and 0.9% (tenfold). The classification of results obtained from the
192 Phytotestkit F Test was based on the hazard classification system for surface waters developed by
193 Persoone et al. [31]. For this purpose, the obtained EC_{50} results were converted into toxic units (TU)
194 using equation (Eq. 2):

$$195 \quad TU = \frac{1}{EC_{50}} \cdot 100 \quad (2)$$

196 The Microtox[®] Toxicity Test was used to assess the inhibition of luminescence in the bacterium
197 *Aliivibrio fischeri* (Microtox[®] Acute Reagent), following the test protocol [32]. The experiments were
198 conducted using a Microtox M500 analyzer. The pH of the leachates was adjusted to the range of 6–8,
199 as specified by the protocol [32]. The inhibition of luminescence in *A. fischeri* was measured after 5 min

200 and 15 min of exposure, in accordance with the Microtox[®] Acute Toxicity Basic Test Procedures. The
201 results were analyzed using MicrotoxOmni software, and all measurements were performed in triplicate.

202

203 **2.6. Data analysis**

204 Mean values were calculated based on triplicate measurements. Comparative analyses of physico-
205 chemical properties, PTE content, PTE bioavailability, and the toxicity of SSL aqueous leachates before
206 and after treatment were performed using the Student's T-test. Post-hoc comparisons were conducted
207 with the LSD (Least Significant Difference) or Tukey's test to find optimal parameters for PTE removal.
208 Correlations between PTE content, PTE bioavailability and the physico-chemical or ecotoxicological
209 properties of SSLs were assessed using Pearson's correlation coefficients in Statistica 13.3 software.
210 Significance levels were set at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, and $p < 0.001$.

211

212 **3. Results and discussion**

213 **3.1. Characterization of untreated digested SSLs**

214 The physico-chemical parameters of the untreated SSLs are presented in **Table 2**. The SSLs
215 exhibited statistically significant differences in the contents of C, N, S, and ash. The analysis of the
216 fertilizing properties revealed a 30% higher P content in SSL1 than in SSL2, with comparable K, Ca,
217 Mg, and TKN contents. No differences in P₂O₅ content were found between the studied SSLs. Both
218 SSLs showed a near-neutral pH and did not differ from each other, indicating an affiliation to the weakly
219 digested category according to the proposed classification [33]. The studied SSLs were observed to have
220 similar EC values, with slightly higher value found for SSL1 (4.3 ± 0.2 mS/cm) than for SSL2 ($3.3 \pm$
221 0.3 mS/cm). The largest differences between the SSLs were noted in the case of DOC. SSL2 ($1319.5 \pm$
222 31.6 mg/L) was characterized by a more than twice higher DOC content than SSL1 (565.5 ± 21.2 mg/L).

223 The pseudo-total contents of the analyzed PTEs in the untreated SSLs are shown in **Table 3**. Among
224 the PTEs covered by the regulations (Zn, Cu, Cd, Pb, Ni, and Cr), Zn and Cu were found at the highest

225 contents in the SSLs, with the lowest values observed for Pb and Cd. Both the contents of the individual
226 PTEs in the SSLs and the differences in their contents between the SSLs mostly resulted from the PTE
227 and SSL types. Despite that the permissible limits for the contents of the PTEs, according to the Council
228 Directive 86/278/EEC [7, 8], are met, the removal of the PTEs from the studied SSLs remains advisable.
229 This will reduce their accumulation in plants and soil organisms, in particular where SSLs are used
230 repeatedly in the same soils over time [34].

231 The determined concentrations of the PTEs in the aqueous leachates from the studied SSLs are
232 shown in **Table S1**, whereas the BI values calculated based on them (**Eq. 1**) are presented in **Fig. S1**.
233 The BI values obtained for the PTEs were primarily determined by their pseudo-total contents in the
234 particular SSL, which were clearly confirmed by the correlation analysis (**Fig. S2 and S3**). An exception
235 was Al which became insoluble in SSL1 due to being bound to the solid fraction as $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ [35]. In
236 SSL2, however, a part of Al was leached, which resulted in a low, but noticeable BI level of 0.28 kg/L.
237 This shows that in this case Al could be present in more mobile forms, such as organic complexes that
238 were more prone to transition to the aqueous phase under near-neutral pH conditions. The DOC
239 concentration, which was more than twice higher in SSL2 than in SSL1, could have played a key role
240 in this process. It is widely recognized that DOC has the ability to form complexes with PTEs, thus
241 increasing their mobility and bioavailability [36, 37], which could explain the higher bioavailability of
242 Al in the aqueous phase of SSL2. The above findings reveal physico-chemical variations in SSLs, which
243 potentially translates into the behavior of many PTEs, with its consequence resulting in different
244 environmental impacts.

245 The highest BI values in the SSL leachates were observed for As, Co, Ni, Mn, and Ag, which
246 suggests their greater mobility and a potential environmental risk. As and Ni differed the most in the BI
247 values between the studied SSLs. In both SSLs, Cd and Pb were characterized by zero bioavailability,
248 suggesting their strong binding to the solid fraction and a low risk of migration to water. The low BI
249 values for Cr, Zn, and Cu indicated their stability in the solid fraction of the SSLs, but their
250 bioavailability was also higher in SSL2 than in SSL1. The literature [38] showed that anaerobic digestion
251 changes the chemical forms of PTEs in SSLs, most often transforming easily available forms into

252 immobile ones. Essentially, most PTEs were immobilized by the OM of a digested SSL and hence a
253 lower level of SSL digestion may reduce the ability of OM to bind PTEs [39].

254

255 **3.2. Effect of PILs on physico-chemical characteristics of digested SSLs**

256 All the PILs caused a decrease in the TOC content in the treated SSLs in the range from 50% to
257 67% (**Table 2**), which indicates the dissolution of OM in the digested SSLs. The high efficiency of the
258 PILs in dissolving lignocellulose has been widely reported, e.g., during the extraction of PTEs from
259 post-consumer waste wood [26] or from willow harvested after soil phytoextraction [25]. The degree of
260 TOC reduction efficiency decreased in the following order: $[\text{H}_1\text{Cim}][\text{HSO}_4] > [\text{TEA}][\text{HSO}_4] >$
261 $[\text{H}_1\text{Cim}]\text{Cl}$. This demonstrates that the presence of HSO_4^- in the PIL molecule contributes to the higher
262 solubility of the biomass of the digested SSLs compared to $[\text{H}_1\text{Cim}]\text{Cl}$.

263 The solvation properties of PILs are greatly influenced by the ions' ability to act as hydrogen bond
264 acceptors/donors [40]. Based on the computed properties of the PILs, it is known that in the case of
265 $[\text{H}_1\text{Cim}]\text{Cl}$ the hydrogen bond donor count is 1, similar to the hydrogen bond acceptor count [41] (**Fig.**
266 **S4**). For the PILs containing the HSO_4^- anion, both counts are higher, respectively 2 and 4 for
267 $[\text{TEA}][\text{HSO}_4]$, while for $[\text{H}_1\text{Cim}][\text{HSO}_4]$ 2 and 5 [41] (**Fig. S4**). As regards $[\text{H}_1\text{Cim}]\text{Cl}$, however, only
268 the cation exhibits the ability to form hydrogen bonds, whereas in the case of the hydrogensulfate-based
269 PILs both the cation and the anion can participate in the formation of such bonds. On the one hand, an
270 increase in the number of potential hydrogen interactions between the PILs and the biopolymers present
271 in the SSLs could have boosted their solvation ability towards $[\text{H}_1\text{Cim}]\text{Cl} < [\text{TEA}][\text{HSO}_4] <$
272 $[\text{H}_1\text{Cim}][\text{HSO}_4]$. But on the other hand, the PILs' pH, decreasing in the same direction (**Table 1**), could
273 have contributed to the observed rate of TOC content reduction. H^+ ions are known catalysts of the
274 hydrolysis of ester, peptide, or glycoside bonds in OM, therefore a lower pH can accelerate its
275 degradation, leading to depolymerization. Both mechanisms (hydrogen interactions and catalytic effect
276 of H^+) promoted the fragmentation of OM macromolecules and the formation of smaller soluble organic
277 compounds, which were partly leached with ethanol, thus leading to the overall loss of TOC. The 1.4-

278 to 3.4-time higher DOC concentrations in the aqueous leachates from the treated SSLs, despite that they
279 were washed with ethanol four times, indicate the presence of residual dissolved OM. This confirms
280 that the PILs degraded OM in the SSLs, leading to the generation of DOC from the existing OM (**Table**
281 **2**).

282 The application of the PILs led to a significant reduction in DIC in the aqueous leachates from the
283 treated SSLs (**Table 2**). This effect was particularly evident in the case of SSL1, for which a 27- to 39-
284 time decrease in DIC concentration was noted, which was due to its much higher initial level, compared
285 to a 6.6- to 18-time reduction for SSL2. The decrease in DIC concentration can be attributed to the acidic
286 environment accompanying the extraction process with the participation of the PILs, in which the
287 soluble forms of hydrogen carbonates and carbonates were transformed into gaseous CO₂ and removed
288 from the SSLs.

289 The pH of the residues after the PIL-based extraction was observed to significantly decrease (**Table**
290 **2**), which resulted from the low pH of the PILs used. A relationship was observed between the pH of
291 the PIL and the pH of the extraction residues, respectively, according to which a lower pH of the PIL
292 solution (**Table 1**) caused stronger acidification of the residues, which may probably be evidence of the
293 PILs' trace residual in the treated SSLs, as indicated by the increased EC of the leachates (by 2.7-18
294 mS/cm, **Table 2**).

295 The PILs did not cause statistically significant changes in the contents of C, H, O, and ash in the
296 SSLs (**Table 2**). However, a significant increase in total N content, including TKN, was noted in the
297 SSLs after their treatment with [H₁Cim]Cl (by 21%) and [H₁Cim][HSO₄] (by 30-33%) or in S content
298 after the application of [TEA][HSO₄] (3.2- to 22-time) and [H₁Cim][HSO₄] (3.8- to 26-time) (**Table 2**).
299 This indicates the incorporation of the rest of the aromatic cations into the structures of the SSLs or into
300 the residual HSO₄⁻ anions originating from the PILs in the treated SSLs. The increase in N content
301 contributed to an increase in the (O + N)/C molar ratio, indicating a higher polarity of OM [42] in the
302 SSLs treated with [H₁Cim]Cl and [H₁Cim][HSO₄] (**Table 2**).

303 [H₁Cim]Cl and [TEA][HSO₄] had a significant effect on the increase in S_{BET} and V_t of both SSLs
304 (**Table 2**). This was probably related to the partial OM degradation, leading to the development of “new”
305 porosity associated with the removal of the compounds blocking the pores, including the extraction of
306 contaminants, or with the disintegration of the aggregates of the SSLs’ molecules. In the case of
307 [H₁Cim][HSO₄], a decrease in S_{BET} was due to the presence of the residue of this PIL in the SSLs after
308 extraction, which is confirmed by the highest values of EC and the highest increase in TKN and S
309 contents (**Table 2**). Due to the highest polarity of [H₁Cim][HSO₄] and its greatest ability to interact with
310 OM, this PIL was the most difficult to be completely leached with ethanol, which could have caused the
311 pores to be covered with the PIL residue and in consequence a decrease in S_{BET}.

312 K, Ca, and Mg (**Table 2**) were not removed from the studied SSLs after treating them with the PILs.
313 These elements occurred in the digested SSLs mainly as crystalline silicates [43, 44], but the PILs did
314 not show the ability to dissolve mineral phases. A significant decrease (by 57-60%) in P was, however,
315 observed after the application of [H₁Cim][HSO₄] and [TEA][HSO₄], with a 16% reduction in P content
316 only in SSL1 treated with [H₁Cim]Cl (**Table 2**). This points out that hydrogensulfate-based PILs,
317 characterized by lower pH, exhibited greater P extraction efficiency than chloride-based PILs, which
318 have weaker acidic properties.

319

320 **3.3. Selection of an effective PIL for PTEs removal from digested SSLs**

321 Among the PILs studied, [H₁Cim]Cl showed the highest efficiency of extraction of 6 PTEs regulated
322 by the EU standard [7, 8] (**Fig. 1**). Regardless of the type of SSL, the highest removal efficiency was
323 obtained for Zn (75-82%), Cd (52-69%), and Cu (43-62%), whereas Pb was removed with a moderate
324 effectiveness (43-45%), while the efficiency for Ni and Cr was ≤ 22%. As far as the other PILs are
325 concerned, such high values for the removal of the investigated metals were not achieved and these
326 values ranged from 5.0% to 70% for [TEA][HSO₄], whereas for [H₁Cim][HSO₄] from 4.0% to 65%,
327 depending on the PTE and SSL (**Fig. 1**). [H₁Cim]Cl was observed to show a preferential extraction of
328 Zn, Cu, and Pb from both SSLs and additionally of Cd, Ni, and Cr, but only from SSL1 (**Fig. 1**). In the

329 case of SSL2, all the three PILs were characterized by a similar Cd removal efficiency, whereas the Ni
330 and Cr extraction effectiveness did not differ between [H₁Cim]Cl and [TEA][HSO₄]. For some of the
331 metals (Ag and Fe), a better efficiency of their removal was sporadically observed after the application
332 of [H₁Cim][HSO₄] and [TEA][HSO₄]. These results demonstrate that the type of anion in a PIL has a
333 significant impact on the effectiveness of extraction of PTEs, whereas the presence of the HSO₄⁻ anion
334 substantially reduces the overall efficiency of this process.

335 The varying results for the removal of the individual PTEs with [H₁Cim]Cl between the studied
336 SSLs depend on the forms of their occurrence in the SSL (**Table S2**). The percentage of the speciation
337 forms of Zn, Pb, and Cr prone to extraction by [H₁Cim]Cl was similar in both SSLs, which is confirmed
338 by the comparable total percentages of these elements in fractions F1–F4. In turn, the differences in the
339 degree of Cu and Ni removal between SSL1 and SSL2 are due to the fact that in SSL1 these elements
340 occurred to a greater extent in forms prone to extraction (fractions F1–F4), whereas in SSL2 their higher
341 percentage was associated with the less prone fractions, e.g., the resistant OM or the mineral structure
342 (fraction F5). For example, in spite of a higher percentage of Cu in forms F1–F4 in SSL2, a more
343 effective Cu removal was observed in SSL1, which demonstrates that Cu in SSL1 was more strongly
344 bound to the soluble OM. A higher percentage of Ni in fractions F1–F4 in SSL1, on the other hand,
345 explains its better removal from this sample.

346 When analyzing the efficiency of removal of the other PTEs (not regulated by the standards) using
347 the tested PILs, it was found that again [H₁Cim]Cl showed a distinctly higher efficiency in removing
348 Co, Mn, As, and Al than the hydrogensulfate-based PILs. Ag and Fe (**Fig. 1**) were an exception because
349 a better removal was obtained in their case (Ag by 83-100% and Fe by 20-36% compared to [H₁Cim]Cl)
350 using [H₁Cim][HSO₄] and [TEA][HSO₄]. This indicates that the lower pH of these PILs (**Table 1**)
351 promoted the solubility of noble metals such as Ag. The lower effectiveness of [H₁Cim]Cl towards Fe
352 is not a major practical limitation because Fe is a beneficial element from the point of view of the soil
353 environment – it is an essential micronutrient for plants and its presence in SSL residue may support its
354 use for agricultural or soil remediation purposes. Taking into account the best extraction efficiency of
355 [H₁Cim]Cl in relation to most of the PTEs, this PIL was selected for further studies.

356

357 **3.4. Mechanisms of PTEs removal by [H₁Cim]Cl from digested SSLs**

358 The differences in the effectiveness of extraction of the PTEs between [H₁Cim]Cl and
359 [H₁Cim][HSO₄]/[TEA][HSO₄] can arise from the differences in the solubility of compounds formed as
360 a result of interactions between the PTEs and the anions of these PILs in aqueous solutions. The PTEs
361 covered by the EU regulations [7, 8] form highly water-soluble chlorides (except for PbCl₂), whereas
362 their sulfate counterparts, such as PbSO₄, are much less soluble than their chloride counterparts. As a
363 result of the presence of the HSO₄⁻ anion, PTEs can be precipitated from an aqueous solution of a PIL,
364 which substantially reduces their effective leaching with ethanol. This can be indicated by the increase
365 in the S content in the SSLs treated with the hydrogensulfate-based PILs ([H₁Cim][HSO₄] and
366 [TEA][HSO₄]) (**Table 2**). In earlier studies, the high efficiency of [H₁Cim]Cl in removing PTEs from
367 SSL was attributed to the coordination ability of the Cl⁻ anion [26] and the possibility of forming both
368 a complex and ionic pair between Cl⁻ and the PTEs [28].

369 Similarly to our study, Abouelela et al. [26] observed a much lower efficiency of [H₁Cim][HSO₄]
370 compared to [H₁Cim]Cl in the case of secondary SSL, which confirms the important roles of the Cl⁻
371 anion in effective removal of PTEs. Inferior results in the extraction of PTEs with [H₁Cim][HSO₄] than
372 for [H₁Cim]Cl were also reported in an earlier study regarding waste wood [23]. The differences
373 between [H₁Cim]Cl and [H₁Cim][HSO₄] were, however, smaller [23] than those observed in our
374 research, which may demonstrate the important roles of the matrix for determining the removal
375 efficiency of PTEs. In our study, the lower removal efficiency of most of the PTEs after the application
376 of [H₁Cim][HSO₄] could result from the difficulty with removing this PIL from the digested SSLs. In
377 spite of many washings, it was only possible to remove a certain part of the added [H₁Cim][HSO₄]. This
378 is confirmed by the increase in the weight of the SSLs treated with [H₁Cim][HSO₄] (recovery at a level
379 of 131-135%), compared to the loss in the weight of the SSLs treated with [H₁Cim]Cl (91-94% recovery)
380 and [TEA][HSO₄] (87-93% recovery) (**Fig. S5**). This was also indicated by the highest values of EC,
381 TKN, and S in the SSLs treated with [H₁Cim][HSO₄] (**Table 2**), despite that four ethanol washing cycles
382 were carried out. The structure of the SSLs after treating them with [H₁Cim][HSO₄] changed from a

383 crystalline structure to an elastic/gel one, which could lead to a partial closure of the pores, hindering its
384 washing, which was also confirmed by the analysis of S_{BET} (**Table 2**). In spite of the highest solvation
385 ability towards OM and the most acidic character among the PILs tested, the retention of
386 $[H_1Cim][HSO_4]$ with the PTEs in the matrix of the digested SSLs may have caused that this solvent
387 proved to be less effective in the extraction of the PTEs than even $[TEA][HSO_4]$.

388 An important new observation from the present study is the selective removal of the individual
389 PTEs, dependent on their type. This suggests that the PTEs that are more weakly bound by the SSLs,
390 thus more easily available, are removed more efficiently by the PILs. Recent studies [45, 46] revealed
391 that PTEs, depending on their type, occur in SSLs in different speciation forms. The correlations
392 between the pseudo-total contents of the individual PTEs in the SSLs untreated and treated with
393 $[H_1Cim]Cl$ and the physico-chemical properties of these SSLs (**Table S3**) enable us to infer which
394 speciation forms of the PTEs are effectively removed by using this PIL.

395 Strong positive correlations ($r \geq 0.950$, $p < 0.05$) between (1) Zn, Cu, Cd, and Pb contents and TOC
396 content, (2) Ni, Cr, and Fe contents, (3) Cu and Mn contents as well as (4) Zn and Cu contents and pH
397 were observed in the case of $[H_1Cim]Cl$ (**Table S3**). At the same time, negative correlations were found
398 between Cu content and EC, S_{BET} , and V_t (**Table S3**). Because in the digested SSLs studied substantial
399 amounts of Zn, Cu, and Pb occurred in the bonds with OM (49-63% for Zn, 67-81% for Cu, and 82-
400 83% for Pb, **Table S2**), the dissolution of OM by $[H_1Cim]Cl$, visible as a decrease in the TOC content
401 in the SSLs (**Table 2**), promoted their significant release into the aqueous solution of the PIL. Although
402 the content of Cd in fractions F1-F5 of the studied SSLs was below the AAS detection limit (**Table S2**),
403 its high percentage in the fraction containing PTEs bound to OM and sulfides in digested SSLs has been
404 confirmed in other studies (71-72%) [38, 47], which also showed a high percentage of Zn, Pb, and Cu
405 (31-93%) in this fraction.

406 The lowest degree of Ni and Cr removal observed in this study, compared to the earlier mentioned
407 PTEs, can be associated with their stronger binding to the matrix of the digested SSLs. In the SSLs
408 investigated, substantial amounts of these PTEs (30-58% for Ni and 56-60% for Cr, **Table S2**) were
409 bound to the crystallographic structure of the minerals, which probably impeded their extraction with

410 [H₁Cim]Cl. The preferential occurrence of Ni and Cr in such bonds (at a level of 42–46% and 45–58%,
411 respectively) has also been demonstrated in other studies regarding the speciation of these PTEs in
412 digested SSLs [38, 48]. The ineffective treatment with this PIL on the ash content in the SSLs (**Table**
413 **2**) and the absence of significant correlations between the contents of the PTEs and ash content (**Table**
414 **S3**) suggest that [H₁Cim]Cl was not able to remove the PTEs from the residual fraction containing very
415 poorly mobilizable PTEs bound in the structures of the minerals.

416 The positive correlations between Ni and Cr contents and Fe content as well as between Cu content
417 and Mn content (**Table S3**) may be an indirect evidence that [H₁Cim]Cl extracted a part of Ni, Cr and
418 Cu from the reducible fraction containing the PTEs bound to Fe and Mn oxides. These compounds
419 exhibited an alkaline/amphoteric nature and hence they could react with the acidic PIL, forming
420 salts/complex compounds with the anion of the PIL and water, which led to the release of the PTEs
421 adsorbed on their surface.

422 The positive correlations between Zn and Cu contents and pH as well as between Cu content and
423 EC (**Table S3**), in turn, indicate the removal of the PTEs from the mobile fractions (exchangeable and
424 carbonates-bound fraction). In the soil environment, exchangeable PTEs can be released as a result of a
425 decrease in pH or a change in the ion composition of the soil water [49]. The treatment of the SSLs with
426 [H₁Cim]Cl lowered the pH and increased EC, which indicates an increase in the concentration of
427 potential competitive cations, including the 1-methylimidazolium cation from the PIL (**Table 2**). The
428 decrease in pH could facilitate the transition of Zn and Cu into the PIL aqueous solution, promoting
429 their removal, whereas the correlation between Cu and EC may suggest an exchange of the Cu cations
430 for the organic 1-methylimidazolium cations of the PIL [50], in accordance with the cation exchange
431 mechanism. Moreover, the increase in S_{BET} and V_t of the treated SSLs (**Table 2**) boosted the availability
432 of Cu, originally enclosed in the structures of the untreated SSLs, which also facilitated its removal.

433

434 **3.5. Optimization of the removal of PTEs from digested SSLs using [H₁Cim]Cl**

435 Due to the highest efficiency of removal of the PTEs from the individual SSLs, the compound
436 [H₁Cim]Cl was selected for further optimization studies. Temperature (90°C and 115°C) (**Fig. 2**), (2)
437 solid loading (S/L ratio: 0.2, 0.35, 0.5) (**Fig. 3**), and (3) number of ethanol washings (washings I, II, III,
438 IV, and Soxhlet) (**Fig. 4**) were optimized.

439

440 **3.5.1. Extraction temperature**

441 It is accepted that the temperature of extraction using PILs is the main factor determining the
442 removal efficiency of PTEs from SSLs [28]. It affects the solubility and mobility of PTEs, which may
443 enhance the efficiency of their removal from SSLs. Furthermore, at a higher temperature the
444 intensification of chemical processes is accelerated, which leads to the decomposition of SSL and, at the
445 same time, the facilitation of the extraction of PTEs.

446 The higher temperature (115°C) (**Fig. 2**) was more efficient in removing the PTEs than the lower
447 temperature (90°C), which was particularly visible in the case of SSL1. As far as SSL2 is concerned, an
448 enhanced efficiency with increasing extraction temperature was observed only for some of the PTEs.
449 The PTE removal efficiency was also clearly dependent on the type of SSL, but the effectiveness
450 changed depending on the PTE type (**Fig. 2**). An increase in temperature from 90°C to 115°C
451 significantly boosted the extraction for both SSLs in the case of Zn (by 33-55%), Co (by 30-68%), Mn
452 (by 55-66%), and Fe (by 39-102%). An enhanced removal of Cr (by 89%), Pb (by 54%), Ni (by 48%),
453 As (by 37%), and Cu (by 28%) was observed only for SSL1, whereas for SSL2 the removal of Ag (by
454 300%) and Al (by 39%) (**Fig. 2**). An effective increase in the removal of PTEs with increasing
455 temperature is explained by a decrease in PIL viscosity, which results in an increase in the mass transfer
456 rate and in the interphase contact area between the PIL and the SSL [28].

457 Nevertheless, significant differences in the removal of the PTEs were observed between the SSLs,
458 which were also determined by the PTE type. At 90°C, the extraction of Zn, Cd, and Pb was higher from
459 SSL2 (54–70%) than from SSL1 (36–53%). Cu was removed efficiently (50–58%) without significant
460 differences between the SSLs. Poorer results were obtained for Al, As, Co, and Mn (25–38%), the lowest

461 ones for Fe, Ni, Cr, and Ag (3.0–23%), whereas Ni and Cr were better removed from SSL2. At 115°C,
462 Zn and Cd were still better removed from SSL2 (71–87%) than from SSL1 (57–70%). Cu was removed
463 at a similar level from the SSLs (63–64%). Cr, on the other hand, was better removed from SSL1. The
464 differences in the removal of Pb and Ni, which had been previously observed between the SSLs,
465 disappeared. Ag and Al were removed more efficiently from SSL2, while As and Co – from SSL1.

466 The higher efficiency of removal of some of the PTEs from SSL2 than from SSL1, especially at
467 90°C, is due to the differences in the chemical composition and sorption properties of both SSLs. The
468 lower ash content in SSL2 (**Table 2**) suggests a limited presence of strong adsorbents of the PTEs, which
469 results in their weaker bonding. Ash is commonly recognized as an effective adsorbent of PTEs and its
470 presence can significantly hinder their extraction [51]. In effect, the PTEs in SSL2 were more weakly
471 bound, which facilitated their removal in the extraction process already at the lower temperature. An
472 additional factor contributing to the higher removal efficiency from SSL2 than SSL1 can be DOC
473 content. The higher DOC content in SSL2 (**Table 2**) can promote the formation of DOC-PTE
474 complexes, increasing the mobility and bioavailability of the PTEs [36, 37], which was associated with
475 a simultaneous increase in the extraction at the lower temperature.

476

477 **3.5.2. S/L ratio**

478 Another important parameter affecting extraction efficiency is the mass ratio of SSL (solid) to PIL
479 solution (liquid) (S/L ratio). Generally, with increasing of SSL mass, the effectiveness of the PIL
480 decreased, but this relationship related only to some of the PTEs (**Fig. 3**). This effect was more
481 pronounced for SSL2 than for SSL1. Regardless of the S/L ratio, the extraction efficiency of Zn, Cu and
482 Cd from SSL1 or only of Zn and Cd from SSL2 remained at a constant level, which suggests that the
483 influence of this parameter can vary and is dependent on both the PTE and SSL type.

484 An increase in the S/L ratio from 0.2 to 0.35 particularly enhanced the extraction of Al, Ag, and As
485 (by 30-73%) and decreased the removal of Mn, Pb, and Fe (by 20-26%) from SSL1. In the case of SSL2,
486 an increase in the S/L ratio enhanced the extraction of Co, Ag, Cr, and As (by 29-231%), but decreased

487 the removal of Fe, Pb, Al, Cu, and Mn (by 17-45%). A further increase in the S/L ratio (from 0.35 to
488 0.5) caused changes in the extraction efficiency only in some cases, but for most of the PTEs they were
489 not statistically significant (**Fig. 3**). It was found that the extraction of Ni, Cr, and As from SSL2
490 weakened to a greater degree (by 26-75%) than from SSL1 (by 19-48%), and additionally the efficiency
491 of extraction of Ag (by 24%) and Co (by 40%) from SSL2, with the improved removability of Ag from
492 SSL1 (by 63%) and Mn from SSL2 (by 28%).

493 The above data demonstrate that the most beneficial effect was obtained for the lower S/L ratios
494 (0.2 or 0.35). The economically more beneficial S/L ratio = 0.35 did not adversely affect the treatment
495 of the SSLs with the PILs at the laboratory scale, increasing the extraction effectiveness of the more
496 difficult-to-remove elements, including Cr, with a minimal reduction in the efficiency for single PTEs,
497 including Cu and/or Pb. The higher removal efficiency of the PTEs at the lower S/L ratio values is
498 associated with a larger reactive surface and a larger contact surface between the PIL and the SSL. In
499 effect, a chance for an interaction between the PIL and the PTEs increases, which promotes a more
500 efficient extraction of the PTEs, especially those that are difficult to remove. Moreover, an increase in
501 the S/L ratio increases the SSL-PIL mixture density which, if the contact time is not extended, weakens
502 the extraction effectiveness of some of the PTEs due to a slower diffusion into the PIL. This effect was
503 particularly visible at the S/L ratio of 0.5 (**Fig. 3**).

504

505 **3.5.3. Ethanol washing**

506 The washing stage after the extraction is necessary not only to remove the residue of the PILs, but
507 also the residue of the PTEs bound to them. As regards the majority of the PTEs, the 1st washing
508 removed most ($\geq 66\%$) of the PTEs (**Fig. 4**). Nevertheless, it was observed that, as previously, the
509 washing efficiency was dependent on the PTE and SSL type.

510 The 1st washing was the most effective and sufficient to remove Zn, Pb, and As from SSL1 (**Fig.**
511 **4a**) as well as Zn, Pb, As, Al, and Fe from SSL2 (**Fig. 4b**), without significant differences in the next
512 cycles. At this stage, most of the Mn, Cu, and Fe was removed from SSL1 (66–82%) as well as Cu, Mn,

513 and Ag from SSL2 (86–94%). During the 1st washing, a moderate efficiency was shown for Cd, Al, and
514 Co in SSL1 (48–58%), and also for Cd in SSL2 (41%). A low removal efficiency was found for Cr, Ag,
515 and Ni in SSL1 (1–14%) as well as for Cr, Co, and Ni in SSL2 (3–10%), which indicates the need for
516 further washings. The next cycles enhanced the effectiveness of removal of these PTEs, reaching values
517 close to the maximum ones after the 3rd or 4th washing. The next washings were specific and dependent
518 on the SSL and PTE type. The Soxhlet extraction increased only the removal of Cr from SSL1 (by 48%
519 relative to the 4th washing) and Ni, Co, and Cr from SSL2 (by 31–58% relative to the 4th washing).

520

521 **3.6. Effect of the treatment of SSLs with [H₁Cim]Cl on the bioavailability of PTEs**

522 **Fig. 5** presents the effect of the PIL-based extraction on the content of bioavailable PTEs in the
523 extraction residue. In both the untreated SSLs and [H₁Cim]Cl-treated SSLs, no presence of Pb and Cd
524 was found in the bioavailable fraction (**Table S1**). However, [H₁Cim]Cl had an impact on decreasing
525 the bioavailable Zn and Ni. This effect was particularly significant in SSL2. The content of Co (by 59%)
526 in SSL1 as well as the content of As (by 38%), Fe (by 82%), and Al (by 100%) in SSL2 was also
527 observed to decrease. At the same time, the content of Fe, Ag, As, Cr, and Al (from 96% to 567%) in
528 SSL1 as well as the content of Cu, Co, Cr, Mn, and Ag (from 41% to 2040%) in SSL2 was observed to
529 increase.

530 The observed reduction in the bioavailability was predominantly associated with the reduction in
531 the pseudo-total content of the PTEs (**Table 3**), resulting from their removal from the SSLs using the
532 PIL. On the other hand, the changes in the physico-chemical properties of the SSLs after treating them
533 with [H₁Cim]Cl could have contributed to an increase in the bioavailable fraction.

534 [H₁Cim]Cl caused a significant (by 1.7-1.8 unit) decrease in the pH of the SSLs (**Table 2**), changing
535 it from neutral to acidic. It is accepted that pH < 6 promotes greater mobility of PTEs in SSLs [52].
536 Nonetheless, it is surprising that at the reduced pH the bioavailability of some of the PTEs was not found
537 to increase. This may point out that the effect of pH was balanced by other factors, arising from the
538 modification of the structure and chemical properties of the SSLs after the application of the PIL. The

539 absence of statistically significant correlations between the concentration of the bioavailable PTEs and
540 the pH of the digested SSLs investigated (**Table S4**) confirms that pH is not the only factor influencing
541 the mobility of the PTEs, which can also be indicated by the observed decrease in the bioavailability in
542 some cases and the irregularity of the changes depending on the SSL.

543 The previously suggested OM degradation changes under the influence of [H₂Cim]Cl, manifesting
544 themselves in the reduced TOC and increased DOC (**Table 2**), may suggest the release of previously
545 (before the treatment) unavailable forms of the PTEs (e.g. occluded in the OM structure) which,
546 depending on the SSL, related to different elements. Furthermore, the increase in the (O + N)/C ratio
547 (**Table 2**), resulting from the incorporation of N together with the PIL, shows an increased polarity of
548 OM in the SSLs, which is additionally confirmed by the increase in DOC concentration. The enhanced
549 polarity of OM could have contributed to the intensification of the interactions of the treated SSLs with
550 water, boosting the mobility of the PTEs. Additionally, the increase in S_{BET} of the treated SSLs (**Table**
551 **2**) is evidence of the higher availability of the particles for contact with water, which could also have
552 expedited desorption of the PTEs from the matrix of the SSLs.

553 In particular, the behavior of the PTEs regulated by standards [7, 8] exhibited a comparable trend in
554 both SSLs. A reduction in the bioavailability of Zn and Ni was observed, no statistically significant
555 changes (SSL1) or an increase in bioavailability (SSL2) in the case of Cu, and a consistent increase in
556 the bioavailability of Cr in both SSLs (**Fig. 5**). According to the literature [53], the stability of the
557 complexes formed between these PTEs and soil OM follows the order: Cr > Cu > Ni > Zn. Based on
558 this, it can be inferred that in the studied SSLs, Zn and Ni were primarily associated with less stable OM
559 (susceptible to dissolution by PIL), whereas part of Cu and Cr remained bound to more stable, less
560 degradable OM fractions. As a consequence, Zn and Ni were removed together with the soluble OM
561 already during PIL extraction, while part of Cu and Cr persisted in the treated SSLs due to the presence
562 of more stable complexes with recalcitrant OM. The change in OM polarity induced by the extraction
563 process weakened these interactions, enabling their subsequent removal during simple water leaching
564 and resulting in the increased bioavailability of these PTEs.

565

566 3.7. Effect of the treatment of SSLs with [H₁Cim]Cl on the toxicity of their leachates to 567 plants and bacteria

568 The residue after the extraction with [H₁Cim]Cl was assessed in terms of its ecotoxicological
569 properties. The EC₅₀ values calculated for the untreated SSLs differed significantly between the SSLs
570 (Fig. 6a). The application of [H₁Cim]Cl had a different effect on the leachates, depending on the SSL.
571 The treatment of the SSLs with [H₁Cim]Cl increased the toxicity of SSL1 (a decrease in EC₅₀ by 14%),
572 but decreased the toxicity of SSL2 (an increase in EC₅₀ by 14%). According to the classification of
573 Persoone et al. [31], the leachates from the untreated SSLs were classified in class IV (10 < TU < 100)
574 (Fig. S6b), which indicates their high acute toxicity to *L. sativum*. After treating the SSLs with
575 [H₁Cim]Cl, the toxicity class did not change.

576 In the case of plants, the small increase in the toxicity for SSL1 can be due to the fact that OM and
577 nutrients (Table 2), being an important element in plant growth, are leached with PTEs. Moreover, some
578 PTEs perform the role of micronutrients necessary particularly at the initial plant growth stages [54].
579 Their removal from the system or a decrease in their bioavailability (e.g. Zn) (Fig. 5a) caused a decrease
580 in the nutritional values of the SSLs, which had an impact on the observed effect. Nevertheless, we need
581 to take into account the fact that these were the leachates that were assessed, whereas the application of
582 treated SSLs can have entirely different long-term environmental effects.

583 Fig. 6b shows the toxicity of the leachates towards *A. fischeri*. As in the case of plants, SSL2 (38.5-
584 39.3%) was characterized by a more than twice higher luminescence inhibition (LI) than SSL1 (15.2-
585 16.2%). Generally, no significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were noted in the inhibition of *A. fischeri*
586 luminescence between 5 and 15 minutes of testing, which is related to the sensitivity of the assay to
587 different types of compounds - water-soluble substances, such as divalent metals, often require a longer
588 exposure time (15 minutes) to elicit a toxic response [55], while organic compounds can affect the
589 bacteria more rapidly, making the 5 minute exposure sufficient for detecting toxicity [56]. The extraction
590 of the PTEs from the SSLs using [H₁Cim]Cl produced different results, depending on the SSL type. In
591 the case of both SSLs, a significant decrease in toxicity was found after treating the SSLs with the PIL,
592 but this effect was more pronounced for SSL2 (78-87%) than for SSL1 (28%). The better toxicity

593 reduction obtained after 15 min. (**Fig. 6b**) suggests that in the case of SSL2 the PTEs were the main
594 factor of the observed toxicity, whereas the much lower toxicity reduction in SSL1 demonstrates that,
595 apart from the PTEs, other factors responsible for toxicity remained in it.

596 The fact that the application of [H₁Cim]Cl in the assays with both plants and bacteria did not result,
597 in most cases, in an increased toxicity of the SSLs deserves special attention. This means that the PIL
598 treatment process did not introduce new risk factors and that the PIL-treated SSLs were not more toxic
599 than the untreated SSLs. What is more, in some cases a substantial decrease in toxicity was noted, which
600 confirms the potential of using [H₁Cim]Cl as an effective tool in remediation and purification of SSLs,
601 while maintaining environmental safety.

602 The statistical analysis results (**Table S5**) revealed very strong correlations between root growth
603 inhibition (RGI) or LI and the concentration of the bioavailable PTEs in the SSL leachates after
604 [H₁Cim]Cl. In particular, RGI positively correlated with the As concentration ($r = 0.951$, $p < 0.05$) in
605 the SSL leachates (**Table S5**). This demonstrates that the increase in the As concentration in the SSL1
606 leachate after [H₁Cim]Cl (by 153%, **Fig. 5a**) caused a statistically insignificant increase in RGI (from
607 48% to 53%, **Fig. S6a**), whereas its lower bioavailability after [H₁Cim]Cl in the SSL2 leachate (by 38%,
608 **Fig. 5a**) can be associated with the reduction in RGI (from 74% to 63%, **Fig. S6a**). These results suggest
609 that the bioavailability of As in SSL leachates is an important toxic factor influencing the growth of *L.*
610 *sativum*, but its effects depend on the chemical properties of As forms present in the leachates and on
611 As concentration. A study conducted by Nouri et al. [57] confirms that As exhibits high toxicity to *L.*
612 *sativum* and its phytotoxic concentration is ≥ 10 mg/L. In our study, however, the concentration of As
613 in the SSL leachates was much lower (0.01-0.03 mg/L, **Table S1**).

614 In the case of LI (for 15 min), on the other hand, positive correlations were found with the Ni ($r =$
615 0.991 , $p < 0.01$) and Zn ($r = 0.988$, $p < 0.05$) concentration and a negative correlation with the Mn
616 concentration ($r = -0.959$, $p < 0.05$) in the SSL leachates (**Table S5**). This indicates that the decrease in
617 the concentration of Ni and Zn in the SSL leachates after the treatment with [H₁Cim]Cl (**Fig. 5a**) was
618 responsible for the reduced toxic effect towards *A. fischeri*. On the other hand, the enhanced
619 bioavailability of Mn after [H₁Cim]Cl in the SSL1 leachates (**Fig. 5b**), associated with the lower LI,

620 suggests its potential stimulating effect, as a trace element, on *A. fischeri*. The results of a study by
621 Teodorovic et al. [58] also confirm the low toxicity of Mn to *A. fischeri*. As demonstrated by Hernroth
622 et al. [59], at low concentrations Mn can support the growth of aquatic organisms, but at high
623 concentrations it becomes toxic to them. Nonetheless, no statistically significant relationships were
624 observed between the toxic effects and the physico-chemical properties of the tested SSLs.

625

626 **4. Conclusions**

627 The treatment of digested SSLs with PILs reduces the content of PTEs in them and, among the PILs
628 investigated, [H₁Cim]Cl showed the highest efficiency in this process. An additional advantage of
629 [H₁Cim]Cl is the weak extraction of total P, which is an important nutrient. For all the PILs tested, the
630 removal efficiency of the PTEs was dependent on the SSL and PTE type. The ability of the 1-
631 methylimidazolium cation in [H₁Cim]Cl to form hydrogen bonds is responsible for dissolving OM in
632 the digested SSLs, but the type of anion is of key importance in removing the PTEs – the chloride anion
633 acts more efficiently than the hydrogen sulfate one.

634 The treatment of the digested SSLs with [H₁Cim]Cl also influenced the bioavailability of the PTEs,
635 leading to its decrease or increase depending on the SSL and PTE. In the case of the PTEs covered by
636 the regulations, [H₁Cim]Cl increased the bioavailability of only Cu and Cr in the SSL leachates. In most
637 cases, the treatment with [H₁Cim]Cl reduced the toxicity of the SSL leachates. The lower concentration
638 of the bioavailable Ni, Zn, and As after [H₁Cim]Cl reduced the toxicity of the SSL leachates, which may
639 improve their environmental safety. The high efficiency of [H₁Cim]Cl in the reduction of the PTEs and
640 their toxicity for SSL2 suggests that this method has a better effect on the digested SSLs, characterized
641 by a lower ash content.

642 The obtained study results revealed that the application of an appropriately selected PIL can be an
643 effective method for eliminating PTEs from SSLs. Owing to PILs' extraction ability and selectivity
644 towards specific ions of PTEs, it is possible to significantly reduce their presence in a contaminated
645 material. It should however be emphasized that the type of SSL has a significant impact on the extraction

646 efficiency of PTEs. The ability to form hydrogen bonds, acidity, the type of anion, and also the speciation
647 forms of PTEs in treated SSL can determine to a large extent the effectiveness of the action of a PIL.
648 After the purification process, the derived SSL, free from toxic contaminants, can be potentially used as
649 a soil amendment to fertilize soils or as a component in degraded land remediation processes, for
650 instance in post-industrial or post-mining areas. Finally, the proposed method expands the possibilities
651 of management of SSLs, while minimizing their toxicity and enhancing their commercial value.

652

653 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

654 **Wiktoria Błaszczyk:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation,
655 Formal analysis, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Karolina Fila:** Investigation, Methodology.
656 **Monika Raczkiewicz:** Investigation, Methodology. **Tadeusz Paszko:** Formal analysis. **Daniel**
657 **C.W. Tsang:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Patryk Oleszczuk:** Writing – review
658 & editing, Conceptualization. **Anna Siatecka:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original
659 draft, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Investigation,
660 Conceptualization, Supervision.

661 **Declaration of competing interest**

662 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
663 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

664 **Data availability**

665 Data will be made available on request.

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669 **Appendix A. Supplementary data**

670 Supplementary data to this article can be found online at

671 **References**

- 672 [1] Wang Z, Lu X, Zhang X, Yuan Z, Zheng M, Hu S, 2024. Ammonium-based bioleaching of toxic
673 metals from sewage sludge in a continuous bioreactor. *Water Res* 256, 121651.
674 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2024.121651>
- 675 [2] Seleiman MF, Santanen A, Mäkelä PSA, 2020. Recycling sludge on cropland as fertilizer –
676 Advantages and risks. *Resour Conserv Recycl* 155, 104647.
677 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104647>
- 678 [3] Huang H, Yuan X, 2016. The migration and transformation behaviors of heavy metals during the
679 hydrothermal treatment of sewage sludge. *Bioresour Technol* 200, 991–998.
680 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2015.10.099>
- 681 [4] Olejnik D, 2024. Evaluation of the heavy metals content in sewage sludge from selected rural and
682 urban wastewater treatment plants in Poland in terms of its suitability for agricultural use.
683 *Sustainability* 16, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16125198>
- 684 [5] Thalassinou G, Petropoulos SA, Grammenou A, Antoniadis V, 2023. Potentially toxic elements: a
685 review on their soil behavior and plant attenuation mechanisms against their toxicity. *Agriculture*
686 13, 1684. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture13091684>
- 687 [6] Kocjan A, Kwasniewska J, Szurman-Zubrzycka M, 2025. Understanding plant tolerance to
688 aluminum: exploring mechanisms and perspectives. *Plant Soil* 507, 195–219.
689 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-024-06745-0>
- 690 [7] EUR-Lex, 1986. EUR-Lex, Council Directive 86/278/EEC of 12 June 1986 On the protection of
691 the environment, and in particular of the soil, when sewage sludge is used in agriculture

- 692 [8] European Commission, 2000. Working document on sludge. 3rd Draft. ENV.E.3/LM, Brussels,
693 27 April 2000
- 694 [9] Naserian ES, Cheraghi M, Lorestani B, Sobhanardakani S, Sadr MK, 2021. Qualitative
695 investigation of sewage sludge composting: effect of aerobic/anaerobic pretreatments. Arab J
696 Geosci 14, 836. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12517-021-07232-x>
- 697 [10] Zhao Q, Liu Y, 2019. Is anaerobic digestion a reliable barrier for deactivation of pathogens in
698 biosludge? Sci Total Environ 668, 893–902. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.03.063>
- 699 [11] Błaszczuk W, Siatecka A, Tlustoš P, Oleszczuk P, 2024. Occurrence and dissipation mechanisms
700 of organic contaminants during sewage sludge anaerobic digestion: A critical review. Sci Total
701 Environ 945, 173517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.173517>
- 702 [12] Tarpani RRZ, Alfonsín C, Hospido A, Azapagic A, 2020. Life cycle environmental impacts of
703 sewage sludge treatment methods for resource recovery considering ecotoxicity of heavy metals
704 and pharmaceutical and personal care products. J Environ Manag 260, 109643.
705 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.109643>
- 706 [13] Tiruneh AT, 2014. Evaluation of the risk of heavy metals in sewage sludge intended for
707 agricultural application in Swaziland. Int J Environ Sci 5, 197–216.
708 <https://doi.org/10.6088/ijes.2014050100017>
- 709 [14] Li S, Fang B, Wang D, Wang X, Man X, Zhang X, 2019. Leaching characteristics of heavy metals
710 and plant nutrients in the sewage sludge immobilized by composite phosphorus-bearing materials.
711 Int J Environ Res Public Health 16, 5159. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16245159>
- 712 [15] Geng H, Xu Y, Zheng L, Gong H, Dai L, Dai X, 2020. An overview of removing heavy metals
713 from sewage sludge: Achievements and perspectives. Environ Pollut 266, 115375.
714 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.115375>

- 715 [16] Pathak A, Dastidar MG, Sreerishnan TR, 2009. Bioleaching of heavy metals from sewage sludge:
716 A review. *J Environ Manag* 90, 2343–2353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2008.11.005>
- 717 [17] Yang S, Hai FI, Price WE, McDonald J, Khan SJ, Nghiem LD, 2016. Occurrence of trace organic
718 contaminants in wastewater sludge and their removals by anaerobic digestion. *Bioresour Technol*
719 210, 153–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2015.12.080>
- 720 [18] Cai G, Ebrahimi M, Zheng G, Kaksonen AH, Morris C, O’Hara IM, Zhang Z, 2021. Effect of
721 ferrous iron loading on dewaterability, heavy metal removal and bacterial community of digested
722 sludge by *Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans*. *J Environ Manag* 295, 113114.
723 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.113114>
- 724 [19] Babel S, del Mundo Dacera D, 2006. Heavy metal removal from contaminated sludge for land
725 application: A review. *Waste Manag* 26, 988–1004.
726 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2005.09.017>
- 727 [20] Elomaa H, Seisko S, Lehtola J, Lundström M, 2019. A study on selective leaching of heavy metals
728 vs. iron from fly ash. *J Mater Cycles Waste Manag* 21, 1004–1013.
729 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10163-019-00858-w>
- 730 [21] Hazra MK, Ghoshal S, Mahata P, Maiti B, 2019. Sulfuric acid decomposition chemistry above
731 Junge layer in Earth’s atmosphere concerning ozone depletion and healing. *Commun Chem* 2, 1–
732 8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42004-019-0178-4>
- 733 [22] You J, Gong Q, Rohde S, Zhang H, Korte C, Gollas B, Luo J, 2024. Non-stoichiometric protic
734 ionic liquids. *J Mol Liq* 413, 125663. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2024.125663>
- 735 [23] Abouelela AR, Tan S, Kelsall GH, Hallett JP, 2020. Toward a circular economy: decontamination
736 and valorization of postconsumer waste wood using the ionoSolv process. *ACS Sustain Chem Eng*
737 8, 14441–14461. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.0c04365>

- 738 [24] Gschwend FJV, Hennequin LM, Brandt-Talbot A, Bedoya-Lora F, Kelsall GH, Polizzi K, Fennell
739 PS, Hallett JP, 2020. Towards an environmentally and economically sustainable biorefinery:
740 heavy metal contaminated waste wood as a low-cost feedstock in a low-cost ionic liquid process.
741 Green Chem 22, 5032–5041. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0GC01241F>
- 742 [25] Dastyar W, Zhao M, Yuan W, Li H, Ting ZJ, Ghaedi H, Yuan H, Li X, Wang W, 2019. Effective
743 pretreatment of heavy metal-contaminated biomass using a low-cost ionic liquid
744 (triethylammonium hydrogen sulfate): optimization by response surface methodology–box
745 behnken design. ACS Sustain Chem Eng 7, 11571–11581.
746 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.9b01457>
- 747 [26] Abouelela AR, Mussa AA, Talhami M, Das P, Hawari AH, 2022. Industrial sludge valorization
748 and decontamination via lipid extraction and heavy metals removal using low-cost protic ionic
749 liquid. Sci Total Environ 835, 155451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.155451>
- 750 [27] Wang H, Zhai Y, Liu L, Liu X, Wang Z, Zhou Y, Huang C, He H, 2024. Efficient removal of
751 heavy metals from sewage sludge using a low-cost protic ionic liquid: Investigation of mechanism
752 and ecological risk. J Environ Chem Eng 12, 112840. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2024.112840>
- 753 [28] Yao JG, Tan S-Y, Metcalfe PI, Fennell PS, Kelsall GH, Hallett JP, 2021. Demetallization of
754 sewage sludge using low-cost ionic liquids. Environ Sci Technol 55, 5291–5300.
755 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.0c03724>
- 756 [29] Oliveira MVS, Vidal BT, Melo CM, de Miranda R de CM, Soares CMF, Coutinho JAP, Ventura
757 SPM, Mattedi S, Lima AS, 2016. (Eco)toxicity and biodegradability of protic ionic liquids.
758 Chemosphere 147, 460–466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2015.11.016>
- 759 [30] BS EN 12457-2, 2002. Characterisation of waste–leaching–compliance test for leaching of
760 granular waste materials and sludges

- 761 [31] Persoone G, Marsalek B, Blinova I, Törökne A, Zarina D, Manusadzianas L, Nalecz-Jawecki G,
762 Tofan L, Stepanova N, Tothova L, Kolar B, 2003. A practical and user-friendly toxicity
763 classification system with microbiotests for natural waters and wastewaters. *Environ Toxicol* 18,
764 395–402. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tox.10141>
- 765 [32] SDI, 1992. *Microtox manual*. Carlsbad, CA: Microbics Corporation
- 766 [33] Środa K, Kijo-Kleczkowska A, 2016. Analysis of combustion process of sewage sludge in
767 reference to coals and biomass. *Arch Min Sci* 61, 425–442. [https://doi.org/10.1515/amsc-2016-](https://doi.org/10.1515/amsc-2016-0031)
768 0031
- 769 [34] Corden C, Bougas K, Cunningham E, Tyrer D, Kreißig J, Crookes M, 2019. Digestate and compost
770 as fertilisers: Risk assessment and risk management options. *Wood Environment & Infrastructure*
771 *Solutions UK Limited*
- 772 [35] Kader MS, Zeng W, Johnston E, Buckner SW, Jelliss PA, 2022. A Novel Method for Generating
773 H₂ by Activation of the μ Al-Water System Using Aluminum Nanoparticles. *Appl Sci* 12, 5378.
774 <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12115378>
- 775 [36] Cai M, Ma T, Que H, Shi B, Liu X, Ke Y, 2024. Investigating the impact of humic acid on copper
776 accumulation in *Sinonovacula constricta* using a toxicokinetic-toxicodynamic model. *Toxics* 12,
777 0. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics12010074>
- 778 [37] Christensen JB, Jensen DL, Christensen TH, 1996. Effect of dissolved organic carbon on the
779 mobility of cadmium, nickel and zinc in leachate polluted groundwater. *Water Res* 30, 3037–3049.
780 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354\(96\)00091-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354(96)00091-7)
- 781 [38] Zdeb M, Pawłowska M, Pacan J, 2020. The influence of anaerobic digestion on selected heavy
782 metals fractionation in sewage sludge. *J Ecol Eng* 21, 27–35.
783 <https://doi.org/10.12911/22998993/118302>

- 784 [39] Lasheen MR, Ammar NS, 2009. Assessment of metals speciation in sewage sludge and stabilized
785 sludge from different Wastewater Treatment Plants, Greater Cairo, Egypt. *J Hazard Mater* 164,
786 740–749. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2008.08.068>
- 787 [40] Wang Z, Gao F, Ji P, Cheng J-P, 2018. Unexpected solvation-stabilisation of ions in a protic ionic
788 liquid: insights disclosed by a bond energetic study. *Chem Sci* 9, 3538–3543.
789 <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7SC05227H>
- 790 [41] Kim S, Chen J, Cheng T, Gindulyte A, He J, He S, Li Q, Shoemaker BA, Thiessen PA, Yu B,
791 Zaslavsky L, Zhang J, Bolton EE, 2025. PubChem 2025 update. *Nucleic Acids Res* 53, D1516–
792 D1525. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae1059>
- 793 [42] Qu X, Fu H, Mao J, Ran Y, Zhang D, Zhu D, 2016. Chemical and structural properties of dissolved
794 black carbon released from biochars. *Carbon* 96, 759–767.
795 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2015.09.106>
- 796 [43] Yuan S-J, Dai X-H, 2017. Sewage sludge-based functional nanomaterials: development and
797 applications. *Environmental Science: Nano* 4, 17–26. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6EN00177G>
- 798 [44] Di Costanzo N, Cesaro A, Di Capua F, Mascolo MC, Esposito G, 2023. Application of high-
799 intensity static magnetic field as a strategy to enhance the fertilizing potential of sewage sludge
800 digestate. *Waste Manag* 170, 122–130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2023.08.005>
- 801 [45] Dąbrowska L, Rosińska A, 2012. Change of PCBs and forms of heavy metals in sewage sludge
802 during thermophilic anaerobic digestion. *Chemosphere* 88, 168–173.
803 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2012.02.073>
- 804 [46] Tytła M, Widziewicz-Rzońca K, Kernert J, Bernaś Z, Słaby K, 2023. First comprehensive analysis
805 of potential ecological risk and factors influencing heavy metals binding in sewage sludge from
806 WWTPs using the ultrasonic disintegration process. *Water* 15, 666.
807 <https://doi.org/10.3390/w15040666>

- 808 [47] Dąbrowska L, 2012. Speciation of heavy metals in sewage sludge after mesophilic and
809 thermophilic anaerobic digestion. Chem Pap 66, 598–606. [https://doi.org/10.2478/s11696-011-](https://doi.org/10.2478/s11696-011-0128-9)
810 0128-9
- 811 [48] Tytła M, 2019. Assessment of heavy metal pollution and potential ecological risk in sewage sludge
812 from municipal wastewater treatment plant located in the most industrialized region in Poland-
813 case study. Int J Environ Res Public Health 16, 2430. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16132430>
- 814 [49] Tessier A, Campbell PGC, Bisson M, 1979. Sequential extraction procedure for the speciation of
815 particulate trace metals. Anal Chem 51, 844–851. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac50043a017>
- 816 [50] Makanyire T, Sanchez-Segado S, Jha A, 2016. Separation and recovery of critical metal ions using
817 ionic liquids. Adv Manuf 4, 33–46. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40436-015-0132-3>
- 818 [51] Cave G, Fatehi P, 2018. Leaching characteristics of biomass fly ash in water and a TMP spent
819 liquor: a case study. J Bioresour Bioprod 3, 145–154. <https://doi.org/10.21967/jbb.v3i4.178>
- 820 [52] Iticescu C, Georgescu P-L, Arseni M, Rosu A, Timofti M, Carp G, Cioca L-I, 2021. Optimal
821 solutions for the use of sewage sludge on agricultural lands. Water 13, 585.
822 <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13050585>
- 823 [53] Merian E, 1991. Metals and their compounds in the environment: Occurrence, analysis, and
824 biological relevance. VCH Verlagsgesellschaft mbH, Germany
- 825 [54] Arif N, Yadav V, Singh S, Singh S, Ahmad P, Mishra RK, Sharma S, Tripathi DK, Dubey NK,
826 Chauhan DK, 2016. Influence of high and low levels of plant-beneficial heavy metal ions on plant
827 growth and development. Front Environ Sci 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2016.00069>
- 828 [55] Rosado D, Usero J, Morillo J, 2016. Assessment of heavy metals bioavailability and toxicity
829 toward *Vibrio fischeri* in sediment of the Huelva estuary. Chemosphere 153, 10–17.
830 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2016.03.040>

831 [56] Mowat FS, Bundy KJ, 2002. Experimental and mathematical/computational assessment of the
832 acute toxicity of chemical mixtures from the Microtox® assay. *Adv Environ Res* 6, 547–558.
833 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1093-0191\(01\)00099-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1093-0191(01)00099-5)

834 [57] Nouri M, Rasafi TE, Haddioui A, 2020. *Lepidium Sativum* L. hormesis induced by heavy metal
835 stress for seed germination and seedling growth. *J Appl Sci Envir Stud* 3, *Appl. Sci. Envir. Stud.*
836 3(4) (2020) 218-231. <https://doi.org/10.48393/IMIST.PRSM/jases-v3i4.22565>

837 [58] Teodorovic I, Planojevic I, Knezevic P, Radak S, Nemet I, 2009. Sensitivity of bacterial vs. acute
838 *Daphnia magna* toxicity tests to metals. *Open Life Sci* 4, 482–492. [https://doi.org/10.2478/s11535-](https://doi.org/10.2478/s11535-009-0048-7)
839 009-0048-7

840 [59] Hernroth B, Tassidis H, Baden SP, 2020. Immunosuppression of aquatic organisms exposed to
841 elevated levels of manganese: From global to molecular perspective. *Dev Comp Immunol* 104,
842 103536. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dci.2019.103536>

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854 **Table 1**

855 Properties of PILs including pH, electrical conductivity (EC) and density (d) of their aqueous solutions
 856 (20% water content, w/w) used for removing PTEs from SSLs.

Ionic liquid/Property	1-methylimidazolium chloride	Triethylammonium hydrogen sulfate	1-methylimidazolium hydrogen sulfate
Abbreviation	[H ₁ Cim]Cl	[TEA][HSO ₄]	[H ₁ Cim][HSO ₄]
Type of cation	Aromatic	Aliphatic	Aromatic
Molecular structure			
Molar mass (g/mol)	118.56	198.26	180.18
Melting point (°C)	72	90.5	64-65
Appearance	Pale-yellow crystals 		
Smell	Odourless	Characteristic odor	Slight aromatic odor
pH	1.55	1.17	0.59
EC (mS/cm)	43.50	10.93	44.70
d ^a (g/cm ³)	1.19	1.19	1.37

857 ^a Density at 25°C (determined by weighting).

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874 **Table 2**

875 Elemental composition, fertilizing properties of SSLs and properties of SSLs aqueous leachates (1:10, w/w) before and after PILs treatment (115°C, S/L = 0.35,
876 45 min, after 4 times ethanol washing).

Sewage sludge	DM ^a	Ash ^b	C ^c	H ^c (%)	Elemental composition				(O + N)/C ^f	TOC ^g %	TKN ^h (%)	Fertilizing properties				pH ^k	Aqueous leachate properties				Surface properties			
					N ^c	S ^c	O ^d	O/C ^e				Ca ⁱ	K ⁱ	Mg ⁱ (g/kg)	P ⁱ		P ₂ O ₅ ^j (mg/100 g)	EC ^l (mS/cm)	DTC ^m	DIC ⁿ (mg/L)	DOC ^o	S _{BET} ^p (m ² /g)	d ^r (nm)	V _t ^s (cm ³ /g)
SSL1	93.60	37.50	27.92	4.71	4.19	1.47	24.20	0.65	0.78	27.41	UNTREATED				6.83	4.27	627.40	61.89	565.51	1.11	23.52	0.007		
SSL2	90.45	33.18	30.09	5.76	5.01	0.20	25.75	0.64	0.78	29.44	4.52	49.5	2.79	4.47	32.71	75.57	6.83	627.40	61.89	565.51	1.11	23.52	0.007	
SSL1	92.75	36.56	27.28	4.31	5.51	1.45	24.89	0.68	0.86	13.70	5.26	45.0	3.09	3.93	25.17	75.34	7.19	1351.50	31.98	1319.52	0.39	18.96	0.002	
SSL2	96.39	35.04	29.61	4.67	6.50	0.50	25.52	0.65	0.83	14.12	[H ₁ Cim]Cl				5.53	6.33	2000.50	4.82	1995.67	3.11	18.66	0.015		
SSL1	93.47	38.54	26.11	4.22	4.40	4.72	22.02	0.63	0.78	11.75	6.38	47.6	3.14	4.04	24.42	87.45	5.01	1902.50	1.79	1900.70	4.99	17.44	0.022	
SSL2	93.21	38.36	24.50	4.09	4.92	4.34	23.79	0.73	0.90	10.12	[TEA][HSO ₄]				4.60	6.98	1956.50	2.58	1953.91	1.01	20.26	0.005		
SSL1	93.82	35.75	26.35	4.31	6.15	5.55	21.89	0.62	0.82	11.42	4.37	52.7	3.96	3.71	14.17	64.23	3.19	1841.50	2.31	1839.18	1.88	25.84	0.012	
SSL2	94.01	34.64	24.91	4.16	6.99	5.19	24.11	0.73	0.97	9.78	5.07	47.9	4.53	3.79	10.92	69.89	4.60	1956.50	2.58	1953.91	1.01	20.26	0.005	
SSL1	93.82	35.75	26.35	4.31	6.15	5.55	21.89	0.62	0.82	11.42	[H ₁ Cim][HSO ₄]				1.87	21.50	1801.85	1.59	1800.26	-	-	-		
SSL2	94.01	34.64	24.91	4.16	6.99	5.19	24.11	0.73	0.97	9.78	6.02	51.9	4.01	3.66	13.12	62.18	1.87	21.50	1801.85	1.59	1800.26	-	-	-
SSL2	94.01	34.64	24.91	4.16	6.99	5.19	24.11	0.73	0.97	9.78	6.82	47.2	4.65	3.72	10.34	68.01	1.93	21.00	1897.49	1.81	1895.68	-	-	-

877 ^a Dry matter content (at 105°C), ^b Residue after combustion at 575°C; ^c Total bulk content; ^d Calculated by difference (100% - Ash - C - H - N - S); ^e Bulk molar atomic ratio corresponding to hydrophilicity index (with
878 increase in this ratio hydrophilicity increases); ^f Bulk molar atomic ratio corresponding to polarity index (with increase in this ratio polarity increases); ^g Total organic carbon; ^h Total Kjeldahl nitrogen (sum of organic and
879 ammonium nitrogen; does not include nitrate nitrogen (NO₃⁻) and nitrite nitrogen (NO₂⁻)); ⁱ Total content; ^j Available content; ^k pH in H₂O; ^l Electrical conductivity; ^m Concentration of dissolved total carbon; ⁿ Concentration
880 of dissolved inorganic carbon; ^o Concentration of dissolved organic carbon; ^p Specific surface area; ^r Mean pore size (diameter) (BET); ^s Total pore volume (d = 1.7 - 300 nm) (p/p₀ ~ 0.99).

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889 **Table 3**

890 Pseudo-total content of PTEs (mg/kg) of untreated SSLs and SSLs treated with [H₁Cim]Cl, [TEA][HSO₄] and [H₁Cim][HSO₄] for 45 min with S/L = 0.35 at a
891 temperature of 115°C after 4 times ethanol washing.

Sewage sludge	Zn	Cu	Cd	Pb	Ni	Cr	Hg	As	Co	Mn	Fe	Al	Ag
UNTREATED													
SSL1	703.4 ± 49.6	135.5 ± 5.42	0.49 ± 0.02	15.8 ± 0.4	74.0 ± 2.7	108.0 ± 2.5	ND	3.10 ± 0.23	4.89 ± 0.44	161.3 ± 12.6	17374.0 ± 1328.5	8489.9 ± 476.0	46.8 ± 2.0
SSL2	958.5 ± 72.1	130.4 ± 1.2	0.72 ± 0.03	14.4 ± 0.6	54.3 ± 3.5	87.2 ± 6.6	ND	3.00 ± 0.27	4.10 ± 0.23	168.9 ± 14.6	9453.7 ± 837.6	8330.8 ± 276.3	41.6 ± 3.6
[H ₁ Cim]Cl													
SSL1	176.4 ± 2.4	52.0 ± 3.4	0.23 ± 0.02	8.72 ± 0.34	58.1 ± 3.8	96.6 ± 7.9	ND	1.98 ± 0.13	2.79 ± 0.24	99.3 ± 5.1	13899.4 ± 1142.1	4583.5 ± 361.8	40.3 ± 2.9
SSL2	172.5 ± 15.1	74.3 ± 5.3	0.22 ± 0.01	8.21 ± 0.46	45.6 ± 1.6	76.7 ± 7.31	ND	0.33 ± 0.03	2.91 ± 0.13	126.7 ± 10.8	8130.2 ± 975.9	5331.7 ± 746.4	32.0 ± 3.8
[TEA][HSO ₄]													
SSL1	474.9 ± 41.3	79.9 ± 5.1	0.46 ± 0.02	11.0 ± 0.7	64.6 ± 3.6	99.1 ± 9.1	ND	2.39 ± 0.16	3.93 ± 0.36	110.5 ± 4.1	14597.8 ± 640.8	6622.1 ± 518.2	34.2 ± 2.7
SSL2	509.7 ± 43.4	96.0 ± 7.3	0.21 ± 0.01	10.1 ± 0.7	46.0 ± 3.6	76.5 ± 4.3	ND	2.01 ± 0.13	3.22 ± 0.17	133.3 ± 11.2	7647.7 ± 550.8	4831.9 ± 422.7	31.2 ± 2.4
[H ₁ Cim][HSO ₄]													
SSL1	407.9 ± 34.1	103.0 ± 7.6	0.47 ± 0.04	13.4 ± 0.7	62.9 ± 1.4	101.0 ± 7.6	ND	2.57 ± 0.04	3.76 ± 0.23	122.6 ± 8.7	13204.3 ± 1102.5	5688.2 ± 245.2	33.7 ± 2.1
SSL2	536.8 ± 30.5	109.5 ± 4.3	0.25 ± 0.004	12.3 ± 0.7	48.3 ± 3.2	80.8 ± 7.5	ND	1.80 ± 0.14	3.49 ± 0.21	143.6 ± 12.8	7941.1 ± 392.5	6331.4 ± 519.2	24.1 ± 0.9
Permissible limits (mg/kg DM)													
EU Directive 86/278/EEC ^a	2500- 4000	1000- 1750	20- 40	750- 1200	300- 400	1000	16- 25	-	-	-	-	-	-
Reg. Min. Environ. 2015 ^b	2500	1000	20	750	300	500	16	-	-	-	-	-	-

892 ^aSuitable for use in agriculture (treated before application onto land, not defined treatment, e.g. digestate from anaerobic digestion, compost or incineration ashes); ^b Polish Regulation of the Minister of the Environment
893 of February 6, 2015 on the use of municipal sewage sludge; suitable for use in agriculture and for land recultivation for agricultural purposes; ND – not determine.

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896 **Fig. 1.** Efficiency of PTEs removal from SSL1 (solid color) and SSL2 (striped color) using PILs at
 897 115°C, S/L = 0.35, and 45 min, after 4 times ethanol washing. Different capital (SSL1) or small (SSL2)
 898 letters indicate statistically significant differences at $p < 0.05$ between different PILs.

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912 **Fig. 2.** Removal efficiency of PTEs from S/L = 0.2 at different temperatures after Soxhlet extraction
 913 when treated with [H₂Cim]Cl for 45 min. Different capital (SSL1) or small (SSL2) letters indicate
 914 statistically significant differences at $p < 0.05$ between treatment temperatures within a given SSL.

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929 **Fig. 3.** Removal efficiency of PTEs at a temperature of 115°C with different S/L ratio after Soxhlet
 930 extraction when treated with [H₂Cim]Cl for 45 min. Different capital (SSL1) or small (SSL2) letters
 931 indicate statistically significant differences at $p < 0.05$ between SSL masses.

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Fig. 4. Cumulative removal efficiency of PTEs at a temperature of 115°C with S/L = 0.35 after different number of ethanol washings, and Soxhlet extraction when treated with [H₁Cim]Cl for 45 min.

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963 **Fig. 5.** Percentage change in the concentration of bioavailable PTEs in SSL1 and SSL2 aqueous
 964 leachates (1:10, w/w) after SSLs treatment with $[H_1Cim]Cl$ at $115^{\circ}C$, $S/L = 0.35$, 45 min, after 4 times
 965 ethanol washing.

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985 **Fig. 6.** EC₅₀ values for SSL1 and SSL2, before and after SSLs treating with [H₁Cim]Cl at 115°C, S/L =
 986 0.35, 45 min, after 4 times ethanol washing calculated based on Phytotestkit F Test **(a)**; *A. fischeri*
 987 luminescence inhibition in 1:10 (w/w) SSLs aqueous leachates (9.1%) before and after SSLs treatment
 988 with [H₁Cim]Cl at 115°C, S/L = 0.35, for 45 min, after 4 times ethanol washing. Different capital (SSL1)
 989 or small (SSL2) letters indicate statistically significant differences at *p* < 0.05 between untreated and
 990 treated SSL within a given time (5 or 15 min) **(b)**.

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Supporting Information for:

Protic ionic liquid-based extraction of potentially toxic elements from digested sewage sludges with ecotoxicological and bioavailability assessment of residues

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This file includes:

Figures S1-S6

Tables S1-S5

1. Materials and methods

1.1. Physico-chemical analysis

The physicochemical properties of samples were determined by standard methods [1]. Dry matter (DM) content was determined by drying samples at 105°C and measured as the residue remained after heating. The amounts of total elemental C, H, N, and S were determined using CHNS EuroEA3000 (EuroVector, Italy) analyzer via catalyzed combustion at 980°C. Ash content of samples was estimated by means of combustion of samples at 575°C for 4 h period and measured as the residue remained after heating [2]. Total O content was determined by subtraction the contributions of determined C, H, N, S and ash from 100% [3]. Total organic carbon (TOC) content was determined with total organic carbon analyzer TOC-L (Schimadzu, Japan). During the analysis, total carbon (TC) was combusted at 900°C, while inorganic carbon (IC) was measured after acidification at 200°C. TOC was calculated as the difference between TC and IC.

Total P content was determined by ashing the sample with CaCO₃ in a muffle furnace (FCF 12 SHM, Czylok), followed by digestion with HCl and HNO₃, and spectrophotometric measurement of the molybdenum-reacted solution at 430 nm (Shimadzu UV-1800, Japan). P₂O₅ content was determined spectrophotometrically by measuring phosphate molybdenum blue intensity in an acidic environment with ScCl₂ as a reducing agent. For the determination of total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN), the SSL samples were subjected to mineralization on a digestion block (FOSS, Poland) in H₂SO₄ with the addition of a copper catalyst at 420°C. Distillation, titration of the distillate with 0.2 N HCl in the presence of H₃BO₃, and determination of TKN were carried out using an automatic analyzer (OPSIS, Sweden). Ca and K were determined by mineralizing samples with HNO₃ in a microwave furnace (CEM Mars Xpress, United States) at 210°C and ~7 atm, followed by dilution with demineralized water. The analyses were performed using a flame atomic absorption spectrometer (Varian SpectrAA 280 FS, Agilent Technologies, United States) and results were verified with blank, duplicate, and certified reference samples.

The pH and electrical conductivity (EC) of the materials were measured using a pH Testr30 (Eutech Instruments, Singapore) and conductivity meter CC-105 (Elmetron, Poland) in the liquid/solid ratio of 10 after filtration through a 0.45-μm membrane [4]. The dissolved organic carbon (DOC) concentration in these water suspensions was determined using TOC-L equipped with 8-port sampler OCT-L.

The parameters of the samples porous structure were determined from low-temperature (77.4 K) nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms obtained from an ASAP 2420 (Micromeritics, USA) surface area and porosity analyzer. Before adsorption measurements, the samples were out gassed at 105°C under vacuum. From the adsorption branch data, using linear form of the BET equation, the specific surface area (S_{BET}) was calculated. Total pore volume (V_t) was calculated from the last point of isotherm ($p/p_0 \approx 1$) and mean pore size (d) was obtained using the **Eq. (1)**, assuming their cylindrical shape:

$$d = \frac{4 \cdot V_t}{S_{\text{BET}}} \quad (1)$$

1.2. Pseudo-total content of PTEs

Determination of the pseudo-total content of PTEs was carried after digestion of 200 mg of untreated SSL and treated SSL using a mixture of HNO₃ + HCl (3:1, v/v) for 1.5 h at 200°C in a microwave oven (Start D, Microwave Digestion System, Milestone, ETHOS EASY, Italy). After the digestion, the samples were cooled down, and the digested solution was passed through a paper filter with pore diameter 22 μm and quantitatively transferred to a flask and diluted to 50 mL. The content of PTEs was determined using Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometer (ICP-OES) (iCAP 7400 Duo Thermo Scientific, USA). Argon (99.9999%, AirLiquide, Poland) was used for the plasma

generation and sample nebulization at flow rates of 12 L/min and 0.5 L/min, respectively. The quantification of PTEs was performed based on the six-point calibration curve prepared for all PTEs in the range from 0.01 to 5 mg/L prepared by diluting a multi-element standard solution (1 g/L) with ultrapure water acidified with 65% HNO₃ (0.5 mL HNO₃ per 50 mL of solution).

The removal degree for each PTE in the SSL samples was calculated using **Eq. (2)**:

$$\text{Removal efficiency of PTEs (\%)} = \frac{C_{\text{untreated SSL}} - C_{\text{treated SSL}}}{C_{\text{untreated SSL}}} \cdot 100\% \quad (2)$$

where $C_{\text{untreated SSL}}$ represent the PTE content in the untreated SSL (mg/kg), while $C_{\text{treated SSL}}$ represent the PTE content of the SSL after treatment. Depending on the number of washing cycles, the mass of the treated SSL was higher (if the PIL was not completely removed) or lower (due to the removal of ethanol-soluble SSL organic matter) compared to the mass of the untreated SSL. In the calculations of PTEs concentration, the mass of the treated SSL was adjusted by multiplying the SSLs initial-to-final mass ratio by the mass of the sample collected for analysis.

1.3. PTEs sequential chemical extraction

Sequential extraction was performed according to the five-step Tessier method [5] to differentiate metal fractions (Zn, Cu, Cd, Cr, Ni, Pb) in untreated SSLs. Dried samples (1 g) were sequentially leached with specific reagents, with shaking or heating depending on the extraction step. After each step, samples were centrifuged, filtered through quantitative paper filters with a pore diameter of 3-5 μm , acidified with HNO₃, and analyzed for PTE concentrations using atomic absorption spectrometer (AAS; Hitachi Z-8200, Hitachi High-Technologies Corporation, Japan). Calibration was performed using the standard addition method. All experiments were conducted in triplicate.

Fig. S1. Bioavailability index (BI) of selected PTEs in the analyzed SSLs.

Fig. S2. Pearson's correlation between the bioavailable concentration of PTEs and their pseudo-total content in SSL1.

Fig. S3. Pearson's correlation between the bioavailable concentration of PTEs and their pseudo-total content in SSL2.

Fig. S4. Hydrogen bond donor/acceptor counts in selected PILs and their relation to solvation ability.

Fig. S5. Yield of SSL with a reduced amount of PTEs (for 115°C, S/L = 0.35, 45 min, after 4 times ethanol washing) relative to untreated SSL.

Fig. S6. *L. sativum* root growth inhibition in 1:10 (w/w) SSLs aqueous leachates before and after SSLs treating with [H₁Cim]Cl at 115°C, S/L = 0.35, 45 min, after 4 times ethanol washing. Different capital (SSL1) and small (SSL2) letters indicate statistically significant differences at $p < 0.05$ between untreated and treated SSL (a); the relationships between *L. sativum* root growth inhibition and concentration of leachates (1:10 (w/w) SSL aqueous leachates (9.09%) and diluted (v/v) aqueous leachates two times (4.55%), four times (2.27%), and ten times (0.91%) before and after treating with [H₁Cim]Cl at 115°C, S/L = 0.35, 45 min, after 4 times ethanol washing (b).

Table S1

Concentration of PTEs (mg/L) in aqueous leachates (1:10, w/w) of untreated SSLs and SSLs treated with [H₁Cim]Cl for 45 min with S/L = 0.35 at a temperature of 115°C after 4 times ethanol washing.

Sewage sludge	Zn	Cu	Cd	Pb	Ni	Cr	As	Co	Mn	Fe	Al	Ag
PTEs concentration (mg/L)												
UNTREATED												
SSL1	0.0663 ± 0.0047	0.0305 ± 0.0026	ND	ND	0.0478 ± 0.0032	0.0003 ± 0.0000	0.0075 ± 0.0003	0.0160 ± 0.0011	0.1748 ± 0.0095	0.2880 ± 0.0189	ND	0.0525 ± 0.0043
SSL2	0.1413 ± 0.0046	0.0338 ± 0.002	ND	ND	0.1385 ± 0.0052	0.0008 ± 0.0001	0.0325 ± 0.0023	0.0075 ± 0.0007	0.0535 ± 0.0049	1.2103 ± 0.0316	0.2365 ± 0.0002	0.0025 ± 0.0137
[H ₁ Cim]Cl												
SSL1	0.0540 ± 0.0035	0.0273 ± 0.0011	ND	ND	0.0280 ± 0.0022	0.002 ± 0.0001	0.0190 ± 0.0009	0.0065 ± 0.0006	0.1890 ± 0.0103	0.5645 ± 0.0445	0.0470 ± 0.0024	0.1195 ± 0.0084
SSL2	0.0530 ± 0.002	0.0478 ± 0.0028	ND	ND	0.0240 ± 0.0019	0.0018 ± 0.0001	0.0200 ± 0.0014	0.0115 ± 0.001	0.1923 ± 0.0113	0.2238 ± 0.0133	ND	0.0535 ± 0.0037

Table S2

Percentage distribution of PTEs fraction in untreated SSLs based on Tessier sequential extraction.

Sample/fraction	F1 (%) Exchangeable fraction	F2 (%) Carbonates- bound fraction	F3 (%) Reducible fraction (bound to Fe-Mn oxides)	F4 (%) Oxidizable fraction (bound to OM and sulfide minerals)	Σ F1-F4 (%)	F5 (%) Residual fraction (bound to crystallographic structure of minerals)
Zn						
SSL1 UNTREATED	1.1	6.4	28.5	62.9	98.8	1.2
SSL2 UNTREATED	0.5	11.6	37.1	49.4	98.6	1.4
Cd						
SSL1 UNTREATED	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
SSL2 UNTREATED	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Cu						
SSL1 UNTREATED	ND	0.5	5.3	66.6	72.4	27.6
SSL2 UNTREATED	1.2	2.6	5.1	81.4	90.2	9.8
Pb						
SSL1 UNTREATED	1.6	ND	1.0	83.5	86.0	14.0
SSL2 UNTREATED	ND	0.5	2.2	82.4	85.1	14.9
Ni						
SSL1 UNTREATED	ND	4.8	18.2	47.1	70.1	29.9
SSL2 UNTREATED	1.5	7.8	6.5	25.9	41.7	58.3
Cr						
SSL1 UNTREATED	3.5	ND	1.6	35.4	40.5	59.5
SSL2 UNTREATED	16.9	0.7	1.3	24.6	43.6	56.4

ND – not detected (below the detection limit of atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS)).

Table S3

Relationship between pseudo-total content of PTEs and elemental composition and aqueous leachates properties of SSLs (untreated SSL1, PIL treated SSL1, untreated SSL2, PIL treated SSL2) based on Pearson’s correlation coefficients.

	Ash	C	H	N	S	O	TOC	pH	EC	DIC	DOC	TKN	P	Fe	Mn	V _i	S _{BET}	d	
[H ₂ Cim]Cl	Zn	-0.3817	0.4051	0.8447	-0.7195	-0.3276	0.0554	0.9854	0.9648	-0.9407	0.7512	-0.7268	-0.6465	0.2370	0.1154	0.9235	-0.9445	-0.9214	0.4804
	Cu	-0.1619	0.3578	0.6876	-0.7435	-0.2111	-0.1508	0.9688	0.9871	-0.9658	0.9076	-0.8700	-0.6689	0.4294	0.2352	0.9805	-0.9531	-0.9687	0.7496
	Cd	-0.4961	0.4710	0.9005	-0.6391	-0.4192	0.1818	0.9503	0.9291	-0.9151	0.6478	-0.6217	-0.5639	0.1082	0.0055	0.8855	-0.9260	-0.8899	0.3490
	Pb	0.0177	0.1017	0.5651	-0.9031	0.0278	-0.3435	0.9667	0.9316	-0.8703	0.9501	-0.9436	-0.8522	0.6039	0.4666	0.8882	-0.8537	-0.8657	0.7760
	Ni	0.6889	-0.6077	-0.1534	-0.9162	0.7186	-0.8882	0.5199	0.4168	-0.2903	0.8139	-0.8695	-0.9423	0.9754	0.9513	0.3444	-0.2529	-0.2949	0.8060
	Cr	0.7285	-0.7394	-0.2546	-0.8725	0.8094	-0.8946	0.3955	0.2615	-0.1224	0.6760	-0.7509	-0.9175	0.9414	0.9800	0.1689	-0.0889	-0.1190	0.6580
	As	0.0652	-0.1774	0.4525	-0.9382	0.2178	-0.3681	0.8334	0.7130	-0.6123	0.7459	-0.7862	-0.9236	0.5787	0.5806	0.6084	-0.6055	-0.5835	0.4971
	Co	0.1492	0.0518	0.4438	-0.8848	0.1076	-0.4531	0.9111	0.8946	-0.8348	0.9921	-0.9813	-0.8373	0.6921	0.5265	0.8691	-0.8098	-0.8417	0.8861
	Mn	-0.3348	0.5352	0.7897	-0.6048	-0.3981	0.0375	0.9446	0.9899	-0.9960	0.8122	-0.7575	-0.5165	0.2486	0.0388	1.0000	-0.9904	-0.9986	0.6425
	Fe	0.8502	-0.8213	-0.4297	-0.7721	0.8971	-0.9627	0.2391	0.1170	0.0188	0.6024	-0.6785	-0.8286	0.9605	1.0000	0.0388	0.0572	0.0136	0.6555
	Al	-0.1586	0.3247	0.6937	-0.7773	-0.1868	-0.1619	0.9839	0.9884	-0.9534	0.9089	-0.8775	-0.7059	0.4426	0.2636	0.9711	-0.9477	-0.9586	0.7334
	Ag	0.0664	-0.1594	0.4629	-0.9461	0.2082	-0.3741	0.8521	0.7373	-0.6386	0.7721	-0.8090	-0.9286	0.5904	0.6369	0.6369	-0.6307	-0.6117	0.5282
	Ash	C	H	N	S	O	TOC	pH	EC	DIC	DOC	TKN	P	Fe	Mn	V	S _{BET}	d	
[TE _A][HSO ₄]	Zn	-0.9586	0.9380	0.9847	0.3522	-0.9688	0.9103	0.9101	0.8837	-0.9588	0.5943	-0.5338	0.5768	0.6780	-0.1185	0.8959	-0.7553	-0.8411	-0.6213
	Cu	-0.6417	0.7631	0.7333	-0.0193	-0.9357	0.8364	0.9388	0.9884	-0.9288	0.9073	-0.8612	0.3304	0.9026	0.1859	0.9753	-0.6594	-0.7391	-0.4554
	Cd	-0.8378	0.9623	0.9046	0.0635	-0.7936	0.5393	0.8076	0.5818	-0.8230	0.4705	-0.4579	0.1708	0.6226	0.1938	0.5744	-0.3007	-0.4261	-0.1681
	Pb	-0.5372	0.8192	0.6850	-0.3364	-0.8780	0.6014	0.9538	0.8634	-0.9039	0.9643	-0.9586	-0.0202	0.9982	0.5238	0.8276	-0.3346	-0.4528	-0.0965
	Ni	0.1805	0.3007	0.0164	-0.9240	-0.2084	-0.2378	0.4053	0.1685	-0.2790	0.6609	-0.7334	-0.7863	0.6811	0.9902	0.0987	0.5126	0.4029	0.7069
	Cr	0.1607	0.3194	0.0341	-0.9137	-0.2040	-0.2521	0.4008	0.1455	-0.2768	0.6328	-0.7070	-0.7918	0.6642	0.9875	0.0763	0.5313	0.4183	0.7211
	As	-0.6480	0.9177	0.7862	-0.2721	-0.8935	0.5847	0.9638	0.8073	-0.9263	0.8714	-0.8660	-0.0079	0.9468	0.4947	0.7753	-0.2998	-0.4320	-0.0768
	Co	-0.2126	0.6326	0.4025	-0.6881	-0.6105	0.2097	0.7600	0.5761	-0.6639	0.8983	-0.9330	-0.4378	0.9295	0.8322	0.5181	0.0915	-0.0357	0.3307
	Mn	-0.7545	0.7741	0.8057	0.2017	0.9536	0.9368	0.9119	0.9974	-0.9328	0.7921	-0.7280	0.5280	0.7957	-0.0288	1.0000	-0.8038	-0.8685	-0.6341
	Fe	0.3120	0.1688	-0.1203	-0.9664	-0.0712	-0.3645	0.2750	0.0422	-0.1430	0.5714	-0.6521	-0.8621	0.5806	1.0000	-0.0288	0.6161	0.5189	0.7900
	Al	-0.6055	0.9056	0.7513	-0.3380	-0.8370	0.4879	0.9236	0.7244	-0.8786	0.8308	-0.8368	-0.1043	0.9199	0.5616	0.6882	-0.1883	-0.3273	0.0312
	Ag	-0.6833	0.9105	0.8092	-0.1871	-0.9415	0.6890	0.9907	0.8902	-0.9629	0.9023	-0.8832	0.1087	0.9589	0.4032	0.8640	-0.4284	-0.5492	-0.2060
	Ash	C	H	N	S	O	TOC	pH	EC	DIC	DOC	TKN	P	Fe	Mn	V	S _{BET}	d	
[H ₂ Cim][HSO ₄]	Zn	-0.4390	0.8810	0.9385	-0.6225	-0.9505	0.9265	0.8873	0.8889	-0.8915	0.6043	-0.5131	-0.5711	0.6743	-0.0394	0.9234	-	-	-
	Cu	0.1315	0.7596	0.6880	-0.8892	-0.9401	0.7446	0.9499	0.9723	-0.9741	0.9416	-0.8964	-0.8571	0.9482	0.4229	0.9018	-	-	-
	Cd	-0.3353	0.9662	0.9238	-0.6697	-0.7921	0.4656	0.8013	0.7500	-0.7446	0.4535	-0.4091	-0.6557	0.6013	0.2615	0.4848	-	-	-
	Pb	0.4955	0.6842	0.4864	-0.9909	-0.7592	0.2987	0.8528	0.8519	-0.8481	0.9544	-0.9678	-0.9951	0.9743	0.8265	0.5440	-	-	-
	Ni	0.8506	0.2415	-0.0294	-0.7512	-0.2638	-0.2744	0.4165	0.4101	-0.4034	0.7042	-0.7795	-0.7912	0.6898	0.9971	0.0106	-	-	-
	Cr	0.8394	0.1748	-0.1014	-0.6548	-0.1349	-0.4269	0.2966	0.2786	-0.2705	0.5681	-0.6549	-0.7040	0.5671	0.9886	-0.1595	-	-	-
	As	0.1991	0.8704	0.7024	-0.9322	-0.7883	0.2840	0.8689	0.8344	-0.8278	0.7711	-0.7711	-0.9376	0.8647	0.6236	0.5242	-	-	-
	Co	0.5962	0.5643	0.3635	-0.9579	-0.6982	0.2783	0.7931	0.8059	-0.8033	0.9738	-0.9920	-0.9621	0.9630	0.8225	0.5861	-	-	-
	Mn	-0.2075	0.7366	0.7710	-0.6698	-0.9302	0.9413	0.8769	0.9051	-0.9099	0.7500	-0.6684	-0.6174	0.7621	0.0215	1.0000	-	-	-
	Fe	0.8869	0.1705	-0.1011	-0.7084	-0.2044	-0.3172	0.3587	0.3558	-0.3493	0.6759	-0.7558	-0.7503	0.6506	1.0000	0.0215	-	-	-
	Al	0.0434	0.7940	0.7421	-0.8653	-0.9626	0.7925	0.9605	0.9806	-0.9826	0.9092	-0.8554	-0.8292	0.9254	0.3225	0.9506	-	-	-
	Ag	0.1494	0.9071	0.7664	-0.9646	-0.8910	0.4583	0.9501	0.9290	-0.9245	0.8519	-0.8347	-0.9575	0.9304	0.5598	0.6847	-	-	-

Marked value are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ (green) or $p < 0.01$ (blue); N = 4.

Table S4

Relationship between bioavailable concentration of PTEs and elemental composition and aqueous leachates properties of SSLs (untreated SSL1, [H₁Cim]Cl treated SSL1, untreated SSL2, [H₁Cim]Cl treated SSL2) based on Pearson's correlation coefficients.

	Ash	C	H	N	S	O	TOC	pH	EC	DIC	DOC	V _t	S _{BET}	d
Zn	-0.7712	0.6391	0.9692	-0.3304	-0.6560	0.5249	0.7558	0.7673	-0.7670	0.3020	-0.2682	-0.7311	-0.0330	-0.7960
Cu	-0.3953	0.6734	0.0827	0.7291	-0.6265	0.5440	-0.3099	-0.1235	-0.0114	-0.3344	0.4288	-0.0469	-0.1695	-0.0184
Cd	0.3495	-0.7192	-0.5895	0.1432	0.5568	-0.1916	-0.5911	-0.7263	0.8030	-0.5551	0.4611	0.8321	-0.5515	0.7943
Ni	-0.7364	0.6094	0.9631	-0.3804	-0.6200	0.4786	0.7865	0.7917	-0.7859	0.3476	-0.3165	-0.7502	0.0116	-0.8130
Cr	0.9529	-0.7230	-0.7046	-0.3829	0.8451	-0.9391	-0.0998	-0.1596	0.2115	0.4300	-0.4710	0.1746	0.6786	0.2600
As	-0.9499	0.6958	0.7141	0.3391	-0.8209	0.9177	0.1272	0.1771	-0.2216	-0.4081	0.4445	-0.1822	-0.6706	-0.2702
Co	0.5423	-0.1068	-0.1866	-0.3885	0.3113	-0.6248	0.2957	0.3382	-0.3484	0.7000	-0.6707	-0.3977	0.9016	-0.3037
Mn	0.7838	-0.6397	0.9653	0.3087	0.6632	-0.5440	-0.7351	-0.7461	0.7463	-0.2722	0.2392	0.7092	0.0651	0.7766
Fe	-0.7428	0.4432	0.8137	-0.2214	-0.5367	0.5589	0.5284	0.4957	-0.4727	0.0311	-0.0286	-0.4218	-0.3269	-0.5105
Al	-0.8130	0.5633	0.8825	-0.1821	-0.6401	0.6240	0.5642	0.5571	-0.5508	0.0556	-0.0376	-0.5044	-0.2950	-0.5888
Ag	0.6816	-0.8514	-0.9126	0.2137	0.7596	-0.4589	-0.7595	-0.8627	0.9198	-0.4775	0.3941	0.9197	-0.2983	0.9316

Marked value are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ (green); N = 4.

Table S5

Relationship between *L. sativum* root growth inhibition (RGI) or *A. fischeri* luminescence inhibition (LI) and bioavailable concentration of PTEs, aqueous leachates properties, fertilizing properties, pseudo-total content of PTEs and elemental composition of SSLs (untreated SSL1, [H₁Cim]Cl treated SSL1, untreated SSL2, [H₁Cim]Cl treated SSL2) based on Pearson's correlation coefficients.

	Bioavailable concentration of PTEs											
	Zn	Cu	Cd	Pb	Ni	Cr	As	Co	Mn	Fe	Al	Ag
RGI	0.7503	0.4483	-	-	0.7319	0.0678	0.9510	-0.5433	-0.8469	0.7483	0.8205	-0.7084
LI	0.9884	-0.1812	-	-	0.9910	-0.5040	0.7251	-0.2423	-0.9593	0.9429	0.9474	-0.7060
	Aqueous leachate properties				Fertilizing properties							
	pH	EC	DIC	DOC	TKN	Ca	K	P	P ₂ O ₅			
RGI	0.3106	-0.4104	-0.2636	0.3290	0.4148	-0.7567	0.2115	-0.8045	0.1792			
LI	0.7580	-0.7532	0.3773	-0.3609	-0.4007	-0.6061	-0.1783	-0.1324	-0.5621			
	Pseudo-total content of PTEs											
	Zn	Cu	Cd	Pb	Ni	Cr	As	Co	Mn	Fe	Al	Ag
RGI	0.3968	0.1533	0.5769	-0.0155	-0.7125	-0.7815	0.1205	-0.0704	0.3246	-0.8112	0.1724	0.1763
LI	0.8868	0.6677	0.9245	0.6472	0.0241	-0.0507	0.7257	0.2532	0.7142	-0.1014	0.6762	0.6139
	Elemental composition											
	DM	Ash	C	H	N	S	O	IC	TOC			
RGI	-0.3821	-1.0000	0.8822	0.8172	0.3374	-0.9527	0.9423	0.7091	0.2424			
LI	-0.8840	-0.6574	0.4928	0.9184	-0.4668	-0.5110	0.3885	0.0700	0.7994			

Marked value are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ (green), $p < 0.01$ (blue) or $p < 0.001$ (gray); N = 4.

References

- [1] Brunner PH, 1978. Methods of analysis of sewage sludge solid wastes and compost
- [2] Abouelela AR, Mussa AA, Talhami M, Das P, Hawari AH, 2022. Industrial sludge valorization and decontamination via lipid extraction and heavy metals removal using low-cost protic ionic liquid. *Sci Total Environ* 835, 155451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.155451>
- [3] Novak J, Lima I, Xing B, Steiner C, Das K, 2009. Characterization of designer biochar produced at different temperatures and their effects on a loamy sand. *Ann Environ Sci* 3, 195–206
- [4] Arteaga JFM, Vodnik D, Kastelec D, Zupanc M, Dular M, Ortar J, Đurić M, Kaurin A, Mihelić R, Lestan D, 2024. Removal of toxic metals from sewage sludge by EDTA and hydrodynamic cavitation and use of the sludge as fertilizer. *Sci Total Environ* 923, 171444. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.171444>
- [5] Kumkrong P, Mihai O, Mercier PHJ, Pihilligawa IG, Tyo DD, Mester Z, 2021. Tessier sequential extraction on 17 elements from three marine sediment certified reference materials (HISS-1, MESS-4, and PACS-3). *Anal Bioanal Chem* 413, 1047–1057. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-020-03063-z>